

PhD. Dissertation

Marcell Tibor Máthé

2024

Instabilities and cross effects in ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals

PH.D. DISSERTATION

Marcell Tibor Máthé

HUN-REN Wigner Research Centre for Physics
Institute for Solid State Physics and Optics

DOI: 10.15476/ELTE.2024.053

Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Science

Head of the School: Prof. Dr. Gergely Palla

Materials Science and Solid State Physics Program

Program Leader: Prof. Dr. István Groma

Supervisor: Dr. Salamon Péter, PhD.

(Senior research fellow)

HUN-REN Wigner Research Centre for Physics
Institute for Solid State Physics and Optics

Budapest, 2024

Contents

Acknowledgements	3
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Liquid crystals in general	5
1.2 Ferromagnetism and ferroelectricity	8
1.3 Ferroelectric liquid crystals	9
1.3.1 Ferroelectric nematic phase	11
1.4 Properties of nematic and ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals	14
1.4.1 Orientational elasticity	14
1.4.2 Electric properties	16
1.4.3 Flexoelectricity	18
1.4.4 Optical properties	19
1.5 Surface effects in liquids	21
1.6 Cross effects in non-centrosymmetric materials	25
1.6.1 Thermomechanical effect in cholesteric liquid crystals	25
1.6.2 Piezoelectricity in liquids	26
Motivation and objectives	28
2 Materials and methods	29
2.1 Microscopy techniques	29
2.2 Used compounds and properties	32
2.3 Sample preparation	33
2.4 Photolithography	34
2.5 Electromechanical experiments	36
2.6 Finite element calculations	37
3 Results and discussion	38
3.1 Ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal thermo-motor	38

3.1.1	Structure of the director field in sessile droplets	38
3.1.2	Temperature gradient induced flow	42
3.1.3	Summary and outlook	45
3.2	Electric field induced surface instabilities	46
3.2.1	Ramification instability of sessile droplets	46
3.2.2	Ramification and labyrinthine instability in liquid bridges	53
3.2.3	Active matter state of ferroelectric nematics	67
3.2.4	Summary and outlook	74
3.3	Linear electromechanical effect in fluid ferroelectric nematics	76
3.3.1	Summary and outlook	79
3.4	Fluid ferroelectric filaments	80
3.4.1	Summary and outlook	89
 A Appendix: Evaluation programs		 91
A.1	Angular velocity of the tracers in thermo-motor effect	91
A.2	Threshold voltage calculation of the ramification instability in the in-plane electrode geometry	92
A.3	Threshold voltage calculation of the ramification instability in the liquid bridge geometry	92
A.4	Calculation of the length of the meniscus line	93
A.5	Trajectory tracking of the febots	93
A.6	Finding the centre line of liquid fibres	94
 Bibliography		 94
 List of publications		 107
 Theses		 109
 Tézisek		 111
 Summary		 113
 Összefoglaló		 114

Acknowledgements

This dissertation could not have been carried out without the outstanding support of a number of people including the direct colleagues, co-workers from abroad, and my family.

First of all, I would like to thank the great guidance of my supervisor Péter Salamon, who always provided me fast and efficient help in my work.

I also wish to express my deepest gratitude to an exceptional researcher Antal Jákli, who offered me the opportunities to work in the Liquid Crystal Institute in Kent. I would also like to express my gratitude to Fumito Araoka for his support during my work in the RIKEN Institute in Tokyo. I am also very thankful for the hospitality of the Complex Matter research group in the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana.

I am indebted to Ágnes Buka and Nándor Éber for the useful discussions, where they shared vast amount of experience in research and helped my work with their deep physical insight.

I am greatly indebted to Hiroya Nishikawa for providing ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal compounds for my studies.

We thank Attila Nagy and Aladár Czitrovsky for providing access to the optical profilometer and László Péter for the help to record scanning electron microscopy micrographs.

Special thanks to the members of the Department of Complex Fluids of the HUNREN Wigner Research Centre for Physics for the cheerful and inspiring atmosphere.

Last but not least, I would like to thank my mother for her tireless devotion and for championing me and to Anita Estók for the useful advices and her unlimited patience.

This work was financially supported by the US National Science Foundation grant DMR-2210083, by the Hungarian National Research, Development, and Innovation Office under Grant NKFIH FK142643 and EIG CONCERT-Japan project FerroFluid. I thank the support by the ÚNKP-23-3 New National Excellence Program of the Ministry for Culture and Innovation from the source of the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Liquid crystals in general

The extent to which liquid crystals have become part of our lives today is reflected in the fact that the reader is most likely reading this dissertation on a display based on liquid crystal technology. Although research on liquid crystals dates back nearly 150 years to the time when Friedrich Reinitzer first documented [1] a cholesterol derivative with two melting points in 1888, there is still extensive research on liquid crystals today all over the world. “Liquid crystals” as a term refers to special phases of matter, in fact, between the fully solid crystalline phase and the isotropic liquid phase of some materials, there can be a wide range of mesophases [2]. In short, liquid crystals (LCs) are usually complex anisotropic fluids built up from organic molecules, called mesogens. LCs do not or partially have translational symmetry depending on the mesophase, but they have usually long-range orientational order. In biological systems, for example in membranes most commonly lyotropic liquid crystals are present, which are the solutions of amphiphilic molecules in a solvent, usually water. In lyotropic LCs, the different types of mesophases depend on the concentration. Compounds that exhibit different mesophases as a function of temperature are known as thermotropic liquid crystals. A mesophase is called enantiotropic if it can be observed in heating and also in cooling, or it can be monotropic if it appears only in cooling. Monotropic phases are usually metastable.

The mesogenic molecules have anisometric shapes, such as rod or disc-like shapes. During my research I used rod-like compounds that are also called calamitics. A molecule structure with rod-like shape is illustrated in Figure 1.1a.

The simplest mesophase of calamitics, is the nematic (N), illustrated in Figure 1.1b. The molecules’ centres of mass are disordered, similar to an isotropic liquid, but the orientation of the molecules has long-range order. The molecules’ long axes fluctuate around an average direction, which is called the director and denoted by a unit vector \mathbf{n} . Due to the lack of translational order, in the N phase the material can be considered as a three dimensional (3D) fluid. The consequence of the orientational order is that the physical quantities characterising the material become direction-dependent (anisotropic) and thus they can be described by tensors. The

(a)

(b)

Phase	Side view	Top view	Property
Isotropic		- 3D fluid - no directional preference	
Nematic		- 3D fluid - uniaxial - no positional order	
Smectic A			- 2D fluid - uniaxial - 1D positional order
Smectic C			- 2D fluid - biaxial - 1D positional order
Smectic B		- uniaxial - hexagonal structure	

Figure 1.1: (a) Molecular structure of a calamitic liquid crystal (5CB), with rod like shape. (d) Schematic illustration of the isotropic phase and liquid crystal mesophases of calamitics. \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{k} denote the director and the smectic layer normal, respectively.

nematic phase is cylindrically symmetric about \mathbf{n} and it also has mirror symmetry in the plane perpendicular to \mathbf{n} , thus the director has head-tail symmetry, meaning $\mathbf{n} = -\mathbf{n}$. We emphasize that in general, the symmetries of the mesogenic phases and that of the constituting molecules are different. For example, the head-tail symmetry of the N phase originates from that the molecules do not have a preferred polar alignment along \mathbf{n} . Approximately half of the molecules are oriented in one direction and the other half of them point oppositely, along the director. As a result, physical vector quantities parallel to the molecules' long axes, such as the molecular dipole moments, average out, making the N phase non-polar.

To theoretically describe the orientational order, we introduce an order parameter, a physical quantity that is zero in the isotropic phase and it has a finite value in the N phase [2]. The tensor order parameter is $\hat{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbb{S}(T)(\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} - \frac{1}{3}\hat{\mathbf{I}})$, where $\mathbb{S}(T)$ is the temperature dependent scalar order parameter and $\hat{\mathbf{I}}$ is the identity matrix and \otimes is the tensor product. $\mathbb{S}(T)$ is used to describe the magnitude of the order, $\mathbb{S}(T) = \langle P_2(\cos(\theta)) \rangle$, where θ is the angle between the long axis of the molecule and

Figure 1.2: (a) Schematic illustration of the chirality: carbon atom bound to 4 different atoms and the mirror image. (b) Twisted structure of the chiral nematic (cholesteric) phase.

the director, P_2 is the second Legendre-polynomial and $\langle \rangle$ is the averaging over the orientational distribution function.

Moving one step closer to the crystalline nature, the molecules gain positional order as they arrange into layers; these phases are called smectics. In smectics, the layer normal vector \mathbf{k} is another characteristic direction besides the director \mathbf{n} . Several types of smectic phases can be distinguished depending on the order of the molecules in the layers and on the angle between the \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{k} vectors. In the smectic phase, the material behaves as a two dimensional (2D) fluid, the layers can slide on each other, flow is possible in the layers, but the movement of the molecules between the layers is hindered. Figure 1.1b shows some of the smectic phases. In smectic A (SmA) and smectic C (SmC) phases the molecules are positionally disordered in the layer, and the director with respect to the layer normal is parallel and tilted, respectively. In case of more ordered smectics the molecules gain positional order in the layers, like in the smectic B (SmB) phase, where the molecules exhibit hexagonal order.

If a molecule cannot be superposed on its mirror image by rotation, translation or conformational changes it is called chiral. A good example is a carbon atom in a tetrahedral bond, where all 4 bonds are connected to different atoms or groups of atoms, presented in Figure 1.2a. The chiral molecules are not mirror symmetric, so they have a left- and right-handed version, called enantiomers. If a LC contains just one type of enantiomer or it is doped by chiral molecules that can induce a twisted structure of the director field. The characteristic length of the twist is called the helical pitch. Along the distance of the pitch the director rotates 360° . The chiral

version of a mesophase is often denoted by a star (" $*$ ") symbol. The cholesteric phase (N^*), is the unique name of the chiral version of the nematic phase. The structure of the N^* phase is illustrated in Figure 1.2b.

1.2 Ferromagnetism and ferroelectricity

Ferromagnetism and ferroelectricity are two distinct yet analogous phenomena observed in materials, each characterised by unique properties arising from the alignment of intrinsic dipoles. Ferromagnetism is exemplified by materials such as iron and cobalt, where atomic magnetic moments align parallel to each other, creating a macroscopic magnetization [3]. The persistence of this alignment in the absence of an external magnetic field results in development of permanent magnets. Quantum mechanical interactions, specifically exchange interactions and spin coupling, govern the manifestation of ferromagnetic behavior.

Conversely, ferroelectricity can be observed in materials with high dielectric permittivity [3]. The defining characteristic of ferroelectricity is the presence of orientable spontaneous electric polarisation. Nonzero polarisation is commonly observed in crystals possessing a polar space group, however this is not a sufficient condition. The ability of orientable dipoles to undergo rotational diffusion under the influence of an electric field is a necessary condition for ferroelectricity to be present [1]. The first ferroelectric material was isolated by Seignette in 1675, called Rochelle-salt [4]. The physical properties connected to the ferroelectric behaviour, like pyro- and piezoelectricity, were investigated first in the 19th century. The term "ferroelectricity" is originated from Schrödinger [4], who introduced it based on the analogy with ferromagnetism, but the first detailed description of ferroelectricity was written by J. Valasek [5]. In ferroelectric crystals, the value of the spontaneous polarisation is typically in the range of $P_s \sim 10^2$ C/m² and the switching time between the different polarisation states with external field is ~ 10 ns [3].

Beyond their scientific importance, both ferromagnetism and ferroelectricity found widespread technological applications. Ferromagnetic materials are crucial in our everyday life like in permanent magnets or in transformer cores. Ferroelectric materials are utilised in non-volatile memory devices, sensors, actuators, and capacitors [6].

Extending the exploration of magnetic phenomena, ferrofluids emerge as a notable class of materials [7]. They are stable colloidal suspensions comprising single-domain magnetic nanoparticles in a base fluid such as water, ethylene glycol, oils or even liquid crystals [8]. The sizes of the nanoparticles are within the range of 10 nm, and they possess a magnetic moment $\sim 10^4 \mu_B$, where μ_B represents the Bohr magneton. The surface of the nanoparticles is treated with a surfactant that prevents aggregation of the particles. Ferrofluids are classified as superparamagnetic [9] rather than ferromagnetic because they do not retain macroscopic magnetisation in the absence of an external magnetic field, in which case the magnetic moments are randomly oriented due to Brownian rotational and translational motions. Ferrofluids are 3D fluids controllable by external magnetic fields, which makes them useful in advanced applications like bioengineering, sensing [10] or even in optical applications based on magneto-optic effects [11].

1.3 Ferroelectric liquid crystals

First time in 1916, Max Born [12] assumed the presence of ferroelectricity in LCs, when he tried to explain the isotropic-nematic transition by dipole-dipole interaction. He assumed that rod-shaped molecules with strong dipole moments can align parallel and form a polar nematic phase. For a long time this concept seemed to be false, since the ordinary nematic phase is apolar. In general, based on symmetry considerations, we must look for those mesophases that has a lack of mirror symmetry (non-centrosymmetric), to find ferroelectric liquid crystals [1].

The topic of ferroelectricity in liquid crystals was mostly studied in the chiral smectic C phase (SmC^*) for a long time [1]. In the SmC^* , there is only one kind of symmetry operation against which the system is invariant, the 180° rotation around the $\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{n}$ axis. The dipole moments parallel to this axis can add up and form a spontaneous polarisation: $\mathbf{P}_s = P_s \frac{1}{\sin\theta} \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{n}$, where θ is the angle between \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{k} . The absolute value of \mathbf{P}_s is in range of $(10^{-5} - 10^{-2}) \text{ C/m}^2$. In SmC^* samples, the direction of \mathbf{P}_s is along $\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{n}$ in each layer; \mathbf{n} rotates along the pitch due to the chirality, causing \mathbf{P}_s to also rotate layer to layer, as illustrated in Figure 1.3a. Macroscopic SmC^* samples usually exhibit no permanent polarisation as the spontaneous polarisation cancels out over a distance equals to the pitch. However, in special cells such as surface-stabilized samples [15] or using external stimulation, such

Figure 1.3: Schematic structures of ferroelectric mesophases: (a) Chiral smectic C phase [13], (b) polar bent-core smectics [1] (c) polar columnar phase of bowl-shaped molecules [14]. μ denotes the molecular dipole moment.

as electric field, the twist structure can be removed, and macroscopic polarisation can be detected. The switching time between polarisation states with an electric field in surface stabilized samples can be as short as $1 \mu\text{s}$, which holds promise for the development of new electro-optical displays [16] and that provided great motivation for SmC*-related research for a long time.

Polar smectic phases can also be formed by bent-core (or banana-shaped) molecules instead of rod-shaped ones [1]. In this case molecules prefer to be oriented in the layers as the molecular arcs are aligned to maximize the space filling. Figure 1.3b shows some of the possible structures of the bent-core smectics, depending on the orientation of the molecules in the layers. In case of SmAP (Figure 1.3b1) and SmCG (Figure 1.3b3) phases the long axis of the molecules and the molecular plane with respect to the normal vector of the layer are parallel and tilted, respectively. When the molecular long axis is parallel but the plane is tilted, it is called SmCP (Figure 1.3b2). An interesting feature of this phase is that it can show chirality even

if the molecules have no chiral atoms thanks to the tilt and the molecular shape. When the arcs of the molecules arrange to the same direction in each layer we get the ferroelectric case; the polar layers alternate, the phase can become antiferroelectric.

If the molecules that form the columnar phase have a shape like a bowl or a cone, they can form polar columns to maximize the space filling as Figure 1.3c shows [1]. Usually, the polar columns arrange to hexagonal or rectangular structure and depending on the neighbouring orientation they can form macroscopically ferroelectric or antiferroelectric phases. The value of the spontaneous polarisation in polar columnar phases is comparable to ferroelectric crystals [17]; their disadvantage is that the polarisation switching time is large, usually in a range of a few seconds.

1.3.1 Ferroelectric nematic phase

Although the mesophases presented above are polar, they cannot be considered as 3D liquids. In terms of flow properties, the apolar nematic phase is the closest to the isotropic liquids. Let assume a polar nematic state, induced by dipole-dipole interaction between the molecules. The molecular dipole moment (μ) should be sufficiently large to withstand thermal fluctuations [18]: $\frac{\mu^2}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon V} > k_B T$, where ϵ_0 and ϵ are the vacuum permeability and the relative permittivity of the molecule, V is the molecular volume, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature. The formula suggests $|\mu| > 6$ D, for $V = 1$ nm³, $\epsilon = 10$, which μ value is larger than the typical dipole moments of ordinary calamitics.

In 2017, two research groups independently published about materials with large dipole moments that exhibit more than one nematic-like phases. One was the compound called DIO by Nishikawa et al. [19] with two different nematic-like phases "M2" and "MP" under the typical nematic phase. It was also shown that DIO exhibits a switchable polarisation with a polarisation value $P_s = 4.4$ $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ in the MP phase. The other mesogen was RM734 synthesised by Mandle et. al [20] (the molecular structure of RM734 is shown in Figure 1.4a). During the phase transition between the nematic phases of RM734, there is a simultaneous occurrence of significant softening of the splay elastic constant and the growth of ferroelectric order [21, 22]. In 2020, Chen et al. [23] showed that in the lower temperature nematic-like phase of RM734 a switchable ferroelectric polarisation can be measured with a saturation value of $P_s = 6$ $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$.

Figure 1.4: (a) Molecular structure of the RM734 molecule and the direction of the molecular dipole moment (μ). Schematic structure of the (b) apolar nematic phase, (c) the ferroelectric nematic phase and (d) antiferroelectric smectic Z_A or splay-nematic (N_s) phase. The black arrows and the colours represent the directions of the molecular dipole moments.

The new liquid crystal mesophase is called the ferroelectric nematic (N_F). Figure 1.4b and 1.4c show the schematic structure of the molecules in the N and in the N_F phases, respectively. In Figure 1.4b-d, red arrows represent the director and black arrows denote the molecular dipole moments, which are parallel to the long axes of the molecules. In the N_F phase, the macroscopic polarisation is along the director. However, due to the polar order, the typical inversion symmetry of the N phase is broken in the N_F phase, consequently the N_F phase is non-centrosymmetric. In spite of the reduced symmetry and the huge spontaneous polarisation, the flow properties of the N_F phase are similar to those of the N phase; it can be clearly considered as a 3D low viscosity fluid [24].

Although the requirements for molecular properties and the mechanism inducing the N_F phase are not entirely clear, it is possible to define some necessary criteria based on molecular dynamics simulations [23, 25] and systematic changes in the molecular structure [26]. As we explained above, the molecular dipole has to be large in the range of ~ 10 D. The alkyl chain at the end of the molecules should be short, as a longer chain may act as a spacer between molecules, creating a separation that blocks the dipole-dipole interactions. Additionally, on the other end of the molecule a group with high electronegativity is required [27]. As we will see later,

the N_F phases of DIO and RM734 are present at much higher temperatures than room temperature. Most recently, a wide range of mesogens and mixtures have been prepared with a polar phase, even such that exhibit N_F phase at or below room temperature [28].

As mentioned in ref. [19], DIO has another nematic-like mesophase between the N_F and N phases. This phase is called the splay-nematic (N_S) or smectic Z_A (SmZ_A) as the molecules have periodic splay structure, illustrated in Figure 1.4d. Due to the periodic splay deformation, quasi layers form with opposite polarisation direction, which makes this phase antiferroelectric. [29]

1.4 Properties of nematic and ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals

1.4.1 Orientational elasticity

Figure 1.5: Schematic illustration of the three basic director deformation types in nematics: (a) splay, (b) twist and (c) bend deformations.

The director may alter in space, which we call a deformed state. Usually, the characteristic length of an orientational deformation is much larger than the molecular size, except at singularities in the director field, which are called defects. In the defect free state, we can use continuum theory to describe the nematic director. In case of a non-polar nematic LC, the contribution of director distortion to the free energy density without surface terms can be written as:

$$f_{elast} = \frac{1}{2}K_{11}(\nabla\mathbf{n})^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{22}(\mathbf{n}(\nabla \times \mathbf{n}))^2 + \frac{1}{2}K_{33}(\mathbf{n} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{n}))^2, \quad (1.1)$$

where K_{11} , K_{22} and K_{33} are the elastic constants corresponding to splay, twist and bend, respectively [2]. Any type of bulk deformation can be split to components corresponding to the splay (Figure 1.5a), twist (Figure 1.5b) and bend (Figure 1.5c) deformations.

To minimise the elastic free energy, the director field would attempt to form a homogeneous structure without deformation in a sample free of boundary conditions and external fields. However, the samples being investigated are always surrounded by some forms of boundary surfaces, which impose boundary conditions on the director field. The description of the surface's orienting ability is called anchoring. If the director is parallel to the normal vector of the interface, it is called homeotropic alignment. Figure 1.6a and Figure 1.6d represents the homeotropic alignment at flat and at curved surfaces, respectively. If the director is perpendicular to the normal

Figure 1.6: (a) Illustration of homeotropic surface alignment when the director is perpendicular to base plate. (b) Ideal rubbed planar alignment: the director is parallel to the surface of the base plate. (c) Realistic rubbed planar surface orientation with pretilt (Θ). The angle of the illustrated pretilt is larger than typical values ($\Theta \approx 1^\circ - 5^\circ$) for better visibility. Representation of the director orientation on the upper surface of a sessile droplet at (d) homeotropic and at (e) planar alignment

vector of the layer that is known as planar alignment (Figure 1.6b and Figure 1.6e). At planar alignment the director has an extra orientational freedom in the plane of the surface that can be set by rubbing the surface along a favourable direction. The non-rubbed planar case is called random (or degenerate) planar, which refers to the random orientation of the director in the plane of the base plate. In a realistic planar orientation, the director is not perfectly parallel to the surface, but is slightly tilted, which can be characterised by the pretilt angle (Θ). The pretilt is typically uniform and it has a small value ($\Theta \approx 1^\circ - 5^\circ$).

The orientating ability of a surface can be described by the anchoring strength: if the director is fixed on the boundary, it is called strong anchoring; if \mathbf{n} can vary due to some influences, such as external fields, it is referred to as weak anchoring. Liquid crystals are usually investigated between parallel glass plates called sandwich cells, where the surfaces are coated by alignment layers to orient the director.

For a sandwich cell, the surface treatment of the two glass plates can be the same as in the so-called planar or homeotropic (Figure 1.7a) cells, or it can be different as in a hybrid cell. In case of a planar cell, also the rubbing directions can vary. In a parallel rubbed cell the rubbing directions are the same (Figure 1.7d), while in anti-parallel rubbed cell (Figure 1.7b) they are opposite.

In case of the N_F phase the spontaneous polarisation tends to align against the rubbing direction, thus as a consequence, the parallel and the anti-parallel rubbed cells behave differently [30]. In the parallel case the direction of the polarisation is almost homogeneous (Figure 1.7e), while in the anti-parallel case the polarisation

Figure 1.7: Liquid crystal sandwich cells with different surface alignments and rubbing in case of nematic and polar nematic phases. (a) Homeotropic cell. Anti-parallel rubbed cell (b) in N and (c) in N_F . In the N_F phase the director has a twist structure in anti-parallel rubbed cells. Parallel rubbed cell in case of (d) N and (e) N_F .

has a twisted structure (Figure 1.7c). Another consequence of the spontaneous polarisation is that the homeotropic alignment is energetically not preferred, because it would generate surface charges. As a result, the techniques used for nematics to produce homeotropic orientation do not work in the N_F phase.

1.4.2 Electric properties

The investigated mesophases N and N_F are uniaxial, as there is one prominent axis, parallel to the director. As a result, the system can be characterised by an anisotropy, i.e. certain physical quantities of the material are direction dependent. Let assume that the director is parallel to the z -axis ($\mathbf{n} = (0, 0, 1)$). In this case, a general physical parameter can be written in the following tensorial way:

$$\hat{\Psi} = \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_{\perp} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \Psi_{\perp} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Psi_{\parallel} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.2)$$

where Ψ can be substituted, for example by dielectric permittivity, the electric conductivity or the magnetic susceptibility. The symbols \parallel and \perp denote the quantity measured parallel and perpendicular to the director, respectively. Because usually not the actual value of Ψ_{\parallel} or Ψ_{\perp} is relevant but their difference, we define $\Psi_a = \Psi_{\parallel} - \Psi_{\perp}$ to characterise the anisotropy of a physical quantity.

When we investigate the effect of electric fields in ordinary liquid crystals, we consider them as leaky insulators. They have low electric conductivity because of ionic impurities, and they behave like dielectrics so the external electric field \mathbf{E}_0

polarise them. The induced polarisation is $\mathbf{P}_{ind} = \varepsilon_0 \hat{\chi} \mathbf{E}$ where $\hat{\chi}$ is the electric susceptibility tensor, and $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 + \mathbf{E}_{dep}$ is the internal modified electric field, which also includes the depolarisation electric field, induced by bound and free charges. The electric displacement is: $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{P}_{ind} + \varepsilon_0 \mathbf{E} = (\hat{\chi} + \hat{\mathbf{I}}) \varepsilon_0 \mathbf{E} = \varepsilon_0 \hat{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E}$ where, $\hat{\varepsilon}$ is the relative dielectric permittivity tensor. The internal electric field can be calculated by satisfying Gauss's law: $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_Q$, where ρ_Q is the density of free charges. By neglecting contaminant ions, let assume that $\rho_Q = 0$.

In the uniaxial case, \mathbf{D} can be transformed to:

$$\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_0(\varepsilon_{\perp} - 1) \mathbf{E} + \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_a \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{E}), \quad (1.3)$$

where $\varepsilon_a = \varepsilon_{\parallel} - \varepsilon_{\perp}$ is the dielectric anisotropy. For conventional calamitics ε_{\parallel} , ε_{\perp} are in range of $\sim 1-10$. The consequence of Eq. (1.3) is that \mathbf{E} becomes inhomogeneous in a deformed director field, since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = 0$ has to be satisfied.

The dielectric free energy density can be written as

$$f_{elec} = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{E} = -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_{\perp} \mathbf{E}^2 - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_a (\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{E})^2 \quad (1.4)$$

Due to the anisotropy, \mathbf{P}_{ind} is not always parallel to \mathbf{E} in contrast to the isotropic case. If $\mathbf{E} \nparallel \mathbf{P}_{ind}$, the field can generate a torque that can reorient the director field. Depending on the sign of ε_a there are two preferred states. If $\varepsilon_a > 0 \rightarrow \mathbf{n} \parallel \mathbf{E}$ and if $\varepsilon_a < 0 \rightarrow \mathbf{n} \perp \mathbf{E}$ is favourable from the point of view of electric energy. To get the equilibrium state of the director field in an external field, the sum of the elastic and dielectric free energies have to be minimised while taking the surface anchoring into account. The external field induced director reorientation is called Fredericksz transition [2].

In case of the N_F phase, the coupling with the electric field is significantly modified by the presence of the spontaneous polarisation (\mathbf{P}_s). The external electric field acts on the material in two ways: on one hand it induces a torque $\mathbf{P}_s \times \mathbf{E}$ that tends to rotate the polarisation along the field, and on the other hand it contributes in the electric displacement, which can be written as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{P}_s + \mathbf{P}_{ind} + \varepsilon_0 \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{P}_s + \varepsilon_0 \hat{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E} \quad (1.5)$$

In regard to the relative dielectric permittivity value, measurements indicate a range of approximately $\sim 10^3 - 10^5$ [19, 31–34], which is significantly larger than in traditional LCs, but the interpretation of experimental results is still under debate [35].

The electric free energy density in case of N_F phase can be written as:

$$f_{elec} = -\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{E} - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{P}_s\mathbf{E} \quad (1.6)$$

It is important to emphasize that the deformation of the polarisation field $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}_s + \mathbf{P}_{ind}$ can induce bound charges in the bulk, with density of $\rho_b = -\nabla\mathbf{P}$, which can significantly increase the free energy, due to the huge value of \mathbf{P}_s . Consequently, the director and thus \mathbf{P}_s tend to avoid splay deformation [35].

The surface charges have also key role in N_F materials, which can emerge at the boundaries due to the polarisation. The surface charge density is $\rho_s = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{u}$ where \mathbf{u} is the normal vector of the surface. Caimi et al. [36] showed that the orientational freedom and the huge value of the \mathbf{P}_s can lead to the formation of surface charges, which can totally screen the electric field in the samples below a threshold electric field, they called this phenomena as superscreening effect.

We note that in the N_F phase due to the spontaneous polarisation induced depolarisation electric field (\mathbf{E}_{dep}), a significant internal electric field can be present, even in the absence of an external field [37]. Therefore, to determine the equilibrium states, it is necessary to consider the term f_{elec} in the total free energy, even in the absence of an external field. Due to the high value of \mathbf{P}_s , f_{elec} can even be dominant in the total free energy. Therefore, homeotropic orientation of the ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals (FNLCs) is generally not preferred [37].

1.4.3 Flexoelectricity

The nematic phase is apolar as the dipole moments of the molecules average out due to the symmetry of the phase. The head-tail symmetry is broken in the ferroelectric nematic phase, which can induce a spontaneous polarisation. However, even in the nematic phase, some deformations, such as splay and bend, can generate polarisation for molecules with pear and bent-shapes, respectively. Such director

Figure 1.8: Simplified visualisation of the origin of flexoelectric polarisation (\mathbf{P}_{fl}). (a) Reorientation of pear-shaped molecules due to splay deformation. In the non-deformed cell, the molecular dipole moments (black arrows) average out, while in the deformed cell a macroscopic polarisation can form. (b) Reorientation of bent-shaped molecules due to bend deformation.

deformation induced polarisation is called the flexoelectric polarisation [1]

$$\mathbf{P}_{fl} = e_1 \mathbf{n}(\nabla \mathbf{n}) + e_3 (\nabla \times \mathbf{n}) \times \mathbf{n}, \quad (1.7)$$

where e_1 and e_3 are the splay and bend flexoelectric coefficients, respectively. The origin of the effect is illustrated in Figure 1.8a and Figure 1.8b for pear- and bent-shaped molecules, respectively. The values of e_1 and e_3 highly depend on the magnitude of the molecular dipole moments ($\boldsymbol{\mu}$). Consequently, in new type of FNLCS, where usually $|\boldsymbol{\mu}| > 6$ D, flexoelectricity can have important role especially in deformed structures, such as in the sessile droplet geometry.

Flexoelectricity is a linear coupling between the distortion of the director by external strain and the electric polarisation, thereby, it is a closely related phenomenon to piezoelectricity [38].

1.4.4 Optical properties

The optical properties of the liquid crystals are also anisotropic, since the refractive indices are in connection with the relative dielectric permittivities considered at optical frequencies (f_{opt}). The parallel and perpendicular refractive indices are $n_{\parallel} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{\parallel}(f_{opt})}$ and $n_{\perp} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{\perp}(f_{opt})}$. The optical anisotropy can be characterised by $n_a = n_{\parallel} - n_{\perp}$. n_{\parallel} and n_{\perp} are often called as ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices, denoted as: $n_{\perp} = n_o$ and $n_{\parallel} = n_e$. Due to different refractive indices, light can propagate at different velocities in the material depending on the light polarisation

Figure 1.9: Determination of the refractive indices by the refractive index ellipsoid. The optical axis (\mathbf{n}) is along the z -axis. The refractive index ellipsoid is marked by the dashed line. \mathbf{k} denotes the wave vector of the light beam (red arrow). The cross section of the plane defined by \mathbf{k} and the refractive index ellipsoid is marked by the red line, which is an ellipse with principal axes n_o and n_Φ .

and the direction of light propagation, which phenomenon is called birefringence. The optical properties of a LC sample with homogeneous director field are similar to those of a uniaxial crystal. The optical axis is the director; along that direction the propagation of light is independent of its polarisation.

Let us consider the director along the z -axis and a linearly polarised light beam with wave vector \mathbf{k} , propagating in a direction that is at an angle Φ with respect to the director. If $\Phi \neq 0$ the light can be split into two components: (1) the ordinary ray with perpendicular polarisation to \mathbf{n} , propagating with c/n_o velocity independently from Φ and (2) the extraordinary ray that is perpendicular to the ordinary ray, propagating with c/n_Φ velocity, where n_Φ depends on Φ . To determine n_Φ we introduce the refractive index ellipsoid as: $1 = x^2/n_o^2 + y^2/n_o^2 + z^2/n_e^2$. Taking the cross-section of the plane determined by \mathbf{k} and the ellipsoid (Figure 1.9) defines an ellipse, which can be used to calculate n_Φ :

$$\frac{1}{n_\Phi^2} = \frac{\cos^2 \Phi}{n_o^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \Phi}{n_e^2} \implies n_\Phi = \frac{n_o n_e}{\sqrt{n_e^2 \cos^2 \Phi + n_o^2 \sin^2 \Phi}} \quad (1.8)$$

In the case, when $\Phi = 0$ and $\Phi = \pi/2$, $n_\Phi = n_o$ and $n_\Phi = n_e$, respectively.

Let assume that the thickness of the sample is L and the propagating light is monochromatic, with wavelength λ . Due to the different propagation velocities of the ordinary and extraordinary components, a phase difference is created between the components:

$$\delta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(n_\Phi - n_o)L. \quad (1.9)$$

This phase difference can induce the changes of the incoming light's polarisation as it propagates through the sample.

Due to the birefringent properties of liquid crystals, the samples are frequently examined by polarisation optical microscopy to investigate the director structure. The polarisation optical microscopy technique is discussed in Chapter 2.1.

1.5 Surface effects in liquids

We investigated the liquid crystals in frustrated geometries, such as in sessile droplet and in liquid bridge geometries. This chapter presents the basic features of the two geometries and their parameters. Later, we show surface instabilities of fluids in external fields that helped us to understand the observed phenomena in FNLCs.

In case of sessile droplets, the liquid is placed on a flat base plate, usually surrounded by air. The shape of a small droplet is determined by the diameter (d) and the contact angle (α), which is the angle formed at the air-LC-solid interfaces. The schematic drawing with the parameters and a snapshot of a sessile droplet are illustrated in Figure 1.10a. If the volume of the droplet is small enough, α is independent from the droplet size, and the shape of the droplet can be approximated by a spherical cap [39]. The value of the contact angle is related to the wetting property of the surface and can be derived from the local minimum of the surface energy by the Young equation [40]:

$$\cos(\alpha) = \frac{(\sigma_{SA} - \sigma_{SL})}{\sigma_{LA}} \quad (1.10)$$

where σ_{ij} is the surface energy between the i, j -th medium, S, L and A denote solid, liquid and air, respectively.

In the liquid bridge geometry, the liquid is in contact with two solid surfaces. If the volume of the liquid bridge is small enough, the shape is determined by the base diameter of the bridge (d), the contact angle α and the distance between the plates (L). The schematic drawing with the parameters and a snapshot of a liquid bridge can be seen in Figure 1.10b.

The surface of the liquids in both geometries is stabilized by the surface tension, originating from the cohesive forces between the molecules. The surface tension tends to minimise the surface of the liquids for a given volume. In case of liquid bridges,

Figure 1.10: Schematic illustration of the investigated geometries with parameters and the corresponding side-view snapshots: (a) sessile droplet and (b) liquid bridge geometry.

if we increase the distance between the bounding plates, the surface of the liquid also increases, which leads to the breakup of the bridge to separated sessile droplets. Liquid bridges formed by Newtonian fluids (described by a constant viscosity) are stable only if their length is smaller than their circumference. The breakup of fluid bridges longer than their circumference is known as the Rayleigh-Plateau instability [40].

In case of non-Newtonian materials, where the viscosity depends on the strain, long slender column of liquids can be stabilised during the pulling for sufficiently high strain rate described by a Deborah number $De = \dot{\zeta} \cdot \tau > 0.5$, where $\dot{\zeta}$ is the strain rate and τ is the relaxation time of a deformation. In such case a strain hardening occurs leading to a homogeneous extensional deformation and a uniform column in the mid-region [1].

A consequence of the Rayleigh-Plateau instability is that it prevents the formation of long and stable fibres from regular liquids. However, in presence of external fields, this effect can be overcome and stable threads with higher aspect ratios can be formed.

It has been known since 1893 that deionized water can form stable slender bridges when subjected to high (> 10 kV) voltages [41]. This phenomenon was revived by Fuchs et al. in 2007 [42] and since then it has been the subject of an intense study

Figure 1.11: Electric field effects in liquids. (a) Formation of water bridge when high voltage is applied between the containers. (b) Schematic illustration of the electrospinning setup. (c) Formation of long thread from polymer solution in presence of strong electric field. The figure (a) is adapted from ref.[42] and (b)-(c) is adapted from ref.[52].

[43–49]. Similar stabilisation effects were observed in ferrofluid bridges in presence of magnetic field [50, 51]. Figure 1.11a shows snapshots of a high voltage stabilized water bridge [42].

Another well-known method in research and in the industry to prepare long fibres on nanoscale from polymer solutions is the electrospinning [52]. A schematic drawing of the electrospinning experiment and snapshots of the thread formation can be seen in Figure 1.11b and Figure 1.11c, respectively. The driving force of the phenomenon is the repulsion between the electric charges on the surface accumulated due to the applied voltage. Above a critical voltage, the repulsive force can break the surface tension and a charged jet emerges from the droplet as Figure 1.11c shows. Depending on the properties of the polymer solution and the strength of the field, different behaviour of the jet can be observed like bending to helical structures or forming branches [52, 53]. Similar effect to electrospinning was observed in ferrofluids called magnetospinning, where in the presence of magnetic field, long threads can be pulled from the solution of magnetic nanoparticles and polymers [54].

Let us consider a ferrofluid droplet placed on top of a base plate. With low enough magnetic field, the surface of the droplet is smooth as the surface tension minimises it. If a magnetic field perpendicular to the base plate is applied, above a

Figure 1.12: Snapshots of magnetic field induced instabilities in ferrofluids. (a) Rosenzweig or normal field instability of a sessile droplet. (b) Labyrinthine instability of a liquid bridge. Figure (a) is adapted from ref. [55] and (b) is adapted from ref. [56].

critical field the surface of the droplet becomes unstable and the formation of spiky structures begins; the instability is called Rosenzweig or normal field instability [7]. Snapshot of the instability is shown in Figure 1.12a.

Another well-known instability of ferrofluids is the labyrinthine instability [7]. In this case the liquid is in a sandwich cell, which is filled partially by the ferrofluid and a non-magnetic liquid (or gas). If the cell is placed in magnetic field applied normal to the plates, the contact line between the two liquid becomes unstable above a threshold magnetic field, resulting in the formation of a maze-like structure, shown in Figure 1.12b. It was shown that the same instability can be induced in dielectrics in presence of electric fields [57, 58].

1.6 Cross effects in non-centrosymmetric materials

Ferroelectric materials have unique properties that are important both for industry and research. In sensor applications, due to their piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties [59], ferroelectric sensors are suitable to measure force, pressure, temperature, and infra-red radiation. As a result, they are widely used in ultrasound medical imaging, sound detection or thermal cameras.

In case of piezoelectricity there is a coupling between the mechanical stress and the electric polarisation, while pyroelectricity involves a coupling between temperature and electric polarisation. In general, these phenomena are called cross effects, and their presence usually depends on symmetry properties of the material. In this chapter, first, we discuss the basic concept of the cross effects by presenting a thermomechanical effect in cholesteric liquid crystals. Later, we discuss the phenomenon of piezoelectricity in non-centrosymmetric liquids and present the possible measurement geometries in which the effect can be experienced.

1.6.1 Thermomechanical effect in cholesteric liquid crystals

In cholesteric liquid crystal droplets, the presence of temperature gradient can induce continuous rotation of the director structure. This phenomenon was first observed by Lehmann in 1900, and it was named after him [60]. A theoretical description was born when Ericksen [61, 62] and Leslie [63] developed the continuum theory of cholesteric and nematic phases. They suggested a description, where the balance equations valid for ordinary liquids are supplemented with a balance equation for the rotation of the director. By this, they proposed a new linear constitutive equation between the possible fluxes and forces in the material.

In the description of the Lehmann rotation [60], the fluxes are the temperature gradient, the velocity gradient and the angular velocity of the director and the associated forces are the heat flux, the stress tensor, and the torque acting on the director. The connection between the fluxes and the forces is presented in Figure 1.13. Between the fluxes and the forces, there can be direct effects (marked by blue arrows in Figure 1.13), such as the Fourier law describing the heat conductivity and there can be also cross effects, which are usually weaker and thus more difficult to measure.

Figure 1.13: Schematic illustration of the direct and cross effects in cholesteric liquid crystals [64]. In case of direct effects (marked by blue arrows), the coupling parameter between the velocity gradient and the symmetric part of the non-equilibrium stress tensor is the viscosity tensor ($\hat{\eta}$), between the temperature gradient and the heat flux is the thermal conductivity tensor ($\hat{\kappa}$) and between the non-equilibrium torque and the director rotation is the rotational viscosity coefficient γ_1 . The illustrated cross effects are the thermomechanical (TM) and the thermohydrodynamical (TH) effects.

If the investigated LC is non-centrosymmetric, there are non-zero coupling parameters between the temperature gradient and the director rotation (marked by green arrow in Figure 1.13) and the flow of the material (marked by red arrow in Figure 1.13), which two cross effects describe the thermomechanical (TM) effect, such as the Lehmann rotation and thermohydrodynamic (TH) effect, where the temperature gradient could induce flow [64].

1.6.2 Piezoelectricity in liquids

A typical cross effect in materials with lack of mirror symmetry is the piezoelectricity [1]. The direct piezoelectric effect, when mechanical stress induces electric polarisation, can be expressed with:

$$P_i = \sum_{jk} \gamma_{i,jk} T_{jk} \quad (1.11)$$

where P_i is the i -th component of the induced polarisation, $\gamma_{i,jk}$ is the piezoelectric coupling tensor and T_{jk} is the stress tensor. The reverse of the phenomenon, when an applied electric field (\mathbf{E}) induces deformation in the material, is the converse (or

Figure 1.14: Possible experimental geometries that allow detection of direct and converse linear electromechanical (piezoelectric) signals in non-centrosymmetric materials, such as FNLCs. (a, b and c): Geometries to detect $\gamma_{z,zz}, \gamma_{x,xz}$ and $\gamma_{z,xx}$, respectively. Top row: Direct effect - Applying strain and measuring electric current; Bottom row: Inverse effect - Applying electric voltage and measuring strain. Red indicates the direction of the ferroelectric polarisation (coordinate systems are chosen so that the ferroelectric polarisation \mathbf{P} is parallel to z -axis). Black (green) double headed arrows represent the applied (induced) strain.

inverse) piezoelectric effect:

$$\zeta_{jk} = \sum_i \gamma_{i,jk} E_i \quad (1.12)$$

where ζ_{jk} is the strain tensor.

In case of materials with lack of mirror symmetry, some elements of $\gamma_{i,jk}$ have to be zero due to symmetry considerations. By choosing the polar axis along the z -axis, any reflection through the x - z (or y - z) plane changes the sign of y (or x). Therefore, all components of $\gamma_{i,jk}$ that contain an odd number of either y or x must be zero. Accordingly, there are only seven non-vanishing piezoelectric tensor elements: $\gamma_{z,zz}$, $\gamma_{z,ii}$ and $\gamma_{i,iz} = \gamma_{i,zi}$, where $i = (x, y)$. Figure 1.14 shows the geometries with the corresponding coordinate systems in which we can expect piezoelectricity in a non-centrosymmetric material such as FNLCs. Figure 1.14a, b, and c illustrate the geometries used to measure $\gamma_{z,zz}$, $\gamma_{x,xz}$ and $\gamma_{z,xx}$, respectively, via direct and converse piezoelectric responses. The direct piezoelectric response involves measuring the strain-induced polarisation, \mathbf{P} , which is related to the current flowing through an electrode area (\mathcal{A}_{el}): $I = \mathcal{A}_{el} \frac{dP}{dt}$. On the other hand, the converse piezoelectric responses involve measuring the applied voltage induced strain.

Motivation and objectives

Conventional nematic liquid crystals have already enabled a technological leap by facilitating the widespread use of flat panel displays. Few years ago a new phase, the ferroelectric nematic was discovered, which exhibits three-dimensional fluidity accompanied by giant spontaneous polarisation, permittivity, and reduced symmetry, compared to conventional nematics.

Our work aimed to reveal the very nature of ferroelectric nematic fluids, which mankind has still limited knowledge about. The dissertation has two major group of topics related to cross effects and electric field induced instabilities in ferroelectric nematics.

In solid ferroelectrics, many interesting phenomena were observed, such as bound charge accumulations as results of temperature gradients (pyroelectricity) or strain (piezoelectricity). We anticipated that these phenomena have yet unexplored analogies in ferroelectric nematics, where the presence of fluidity will give rise to even more complex and unseen spectacular effects.

Since ferroelectric nematics form a new family of materials, during the research work I was also inspired by earlier investigations related to ferrofluids, as the two systems are analogous. Ferrofluids exhibit various interfacial instabilities in presence of magnetic field, such as the normal field [7, 65, 66] and the labyrinthine instability [7, 58, 67–74]. These two phenomena are well established both theoretically and experimentally. Due to the analogy between ferrofluids and polar nematics, it is worthwhile to examine, what kind of instabilities can arise in ferroelectric nematics in the presence of electric field. Besides the analogy, there are also some important differences, whose influences are interesting to consider. The main difference between the two types of complex fluids is that ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals (FNLCs) can be one component systems of organic molecules, while ferrofluids are colloids of nanoparticles. Furthermore, in the electric case, free charges may play a significant role, while in the magnetic case, there are no free monopoles.

Chapter 2: Materials and methods

2.1 Microscopy techniques

Figure 2.1: Schematic drawing of a liquid crystal sample between crossed polarisers and illustration of the azimuthal angle φ between the projection of director and the polariser.

To investigate samples with birefringence, such as liquid crystals, we used polarising optical microscopy (POM). The structure of a polarising optical microscope is similar to that of a simple transmission mode optical microscope, with two additional linear polarisers in the light path before and after the sample. Linear polarisers are optical filters that only transmit light with polarisation along the transmitting axis of the polariser. The second polariser is also called analyser. The polarisers are typically set to be crossed, when the transmitting axis of the polariser and the analyser are perpendicular to each other.

Let's consider a monochromatic unpolarised light source and crossed polarisers. If there is no birefringent sample in the light path, black image can be observed in the microscope as the polariser and the analyser filter out all components of the incoming light. If a nematic LC sample is placed in the light path as illustrated in Figure 2.1, the transmitted intensity is:

$$\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{I}_0 \sin^2(2\varphi) \sin^2(\delta/2), \quad (2.1)$$

where \mathcal{I}_0 is the initial intensity of the light beam, φ is the azimuthal angle between the axis of the polariser and the projection of director onto the sample plane (perpendicular to the light propagation direction) and δ is the phase difference (or retardation), calculated by Eq. 1.9. If the director is parallel to one of the polarisers

Figure 2.2: The Michel-Lévy diagram. Illustration of the visible colours at different effective birefringence and sample thickness for samples placed between crossed polarisers with white light illumination. Adapted from ref. [75]

($\varphi = 0$ or $\varphi = \pi/2$), the transmitted light intensity is zero. Considering the periodicity of the second sine factor, the retardation is classified into orders as: $[0, 2\pi]$ - first order, $[2\pi, 4\pi]$ - second order, and so on.

If the incoming light is polychromatic (white), the components with different wavelengths suffer different phase shifts during the propagation in the sample, thus the observed image in the microscope becomes coloured. The observed colour depends on the effective birefringence ($\Delta n = n_\phi - n_o$) and the thickness of the sample (L); which dependence for white light can be illustrated by the Michel-Lévy diagram shown in Figure 2.2.

A common accessory of polarising microscopes is the lambda plate or full-wave plate, which can be used to add an additional 2π (at $\lambda = 540$ nm and $\varphi = \pi/4$) phase shift to the retardation. The insertion of the full-wave plate into the light path changes the colours seen in the microscope, since the extra 2π phase shift is true only for the above (green) wavelength, and for other wavelengths the added retardation is different. The lambda plate can be used to get information of the director's orientation in the sample plane. If the director is parallel (perpendicular) to the axis of the lambda plate, the retardation of the sample is added to (subtracted from) the additional phase shift. The technique involving the lambda plate provides an opportunity to determine whether the director is parallel or perpendicular to the axis of the lambda plate by the colour. For example, by using only crossed polarisers, the director at $\varphi = \pm\pi/4$ cannot be distinguished according to Eq. 2.1. For a liquid crystal sample where the retardation is in first order, if the director is parallel to

the axis of the lambda plate, an orange-yellow colour can be seen, and blue in the case of a perpendicular orientation.

In the investigations covered by this dissertation, several types of polarizing microscopes were used including Leica DMRX, Zeiss Axio Imager1, Nikon Eclipse Ti2-A, and even custom-made ones. The micrographs were recorded by digital cameras including Flir Blackfly S U3-32S4C and Hayear HY-500B. High speed imaging was performed by a Photron Mini AX100 camera.

In all microscopy related experiments, we used to following heating stages to maintain the temperature of the samples, which is crucial for liquid crystals: Linkam LTS350 (with TMS94 controller), Instec MK1, and Instec HCS402 (with Mk1000 controller) that all provided a temperature stability better than 0.1 °C.

Electrooptical measurements were performed together with microscopy. Micrographs were recorded automatically as a function of diferent voltage signals switched to the samples by experimental systems controlled by custom software implemented in Labview. The signals of function generators (Tiepie HS3, Agilent 33500) were amplified by high voltage amplifiers (FLC A800DI, FLC F1020). All displayed voltages in the dissertation are rms values.

In the experiments related to fibres, electric current measurements were also performed synchronised to the image aquisition. The current flowing in the circuit involving the sample was measured by a Stanford Research Systems SR570 low-noise current sensitive preamplifier connected to a TiePie Handyscope HS5 oscilloscope.

Optical profilometry measurements were performed with a Zygo NewView 7100 3D white light interferometric profiler using Mirau interferometric objectives.

To get more detailed information of the orientation of the director in the sample plane, polarimetric microscopy technique [76] can be used. According to [76], variable birefringent optical elements placed into the light path of the microscope can be used to change the polarisation state of the input light in a controlled way and analyse the transmitted light quantitatively. By taking images of the sample with several settings of the variable retarders, the retardation of the sample (δ) and the azimuth angle of the director (φ) can be calculated pixelwise.

In case of thick samples, such as threads, the polarimetric microscopy technique cannot be used well. To determine the director orientation in fibres, a small percentage (less than 0.1 wt %) of disperse orange 3 (Sigma Aldrich) dichroic dye was added to the liquid crystal and a single-colour LED with the peak wavelength of 458

Figure 2.3: (a)-(b) Chemical structure and the transition temperatures (in ° C) of RM734 and DIO ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals. (c) Phase sequence of the FNLC-919 mixture exhibiting the N_F phase at room temperature.

nm was used for sample illumination. The dichroic dye doped liquid crystal sample exhibits the largest (smallest) light absorption for the light polarisation along (perpendicular to) the director.

2.2 Used compounds and properties

During our studies, we used the 4-[(4-nitrophenyl)carbonyl]phenyl 2,4-dimethoxybenzoate (RM734) [20] and the FNLC-919 ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals. The RM734 was purchased from Instec (USA) and the FNLC-919 was obtained from Merck (Germany). Some of the measurements presented for RM734 were also tested by using (2, 3', 4', 5'-tetrafluoro-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl 2,6-difluoro-4-(5-propyl-1,3-dioxan-2-yl) benzoate) (DIO) [19], another prototype compound of FNLCs got from Hiroya Nishikawa (RIKEN Center for Emergent Matter Science, Wako, Japan). The chemical structures and the phase sequences of the used compounds are presented in Figure 2.3. The FNLC-919 is a mixture of highly polar nitrile compounds with undisclosed composition. The ferroelectric nematic phase is monotropic in the used compounds. The phase sequence of the RM734 in cooling: Iso-195° C- N -133° C- N_F -70° C-Cr, where Iso and Cr denote the isotropic and crystal phases, respectively. The mesophases of FNLC-919 are: Iso-80° C- N_1 -44° C- N -32° C- N_F -8° C-Cr, where N_1 denotes a secondary, yet unexplored nematic-like phase.

In case of RM734, we observed that heating up the sample to the isotropic phase for a couple of seconds can help to prevent crystallization and to obtain more homogeneous surface orientation in the N_F phase. However, we also noticed that keeping the sample for a long time in the isotropic phase can damage the material, which results in a shift of phase transition temperatures.

Figure 2.4: (a) Image of the custom made setup made to prepare droplets. (I) Long distance microscopes for vertical and side view. (II) Micropositioners of the heating stage and the teflon bar holder. Magnified part of the image with (III) the teflon bar and (IV) heating stage with a hole in the middle. (b) Side view snapshot of a sessile droplet and illustration of the contact angle calculation. d denotes the diameter of the drop and d_c is the diameter of the fitted circle.

2.3 Sample preparation

The preparation of the sessile droplets and the liquid bridges were made by a custom-made setup, which is suitable to control the size of the droplets. The flat glass substrates, served as base plates for droplets, were cleaned by applying the following procedure: (1) rubbing with ethanol for 2 min (2) sonication in ethanol for 15 min (3) rinsing by DI – H₂O (deionized water) (4) sonication in DI – H₂O for 15 min two times by changing the water (5) drying by a stream of clean air (6) annealing at 90°C for 10 min (7) plasma cleaning for 5 min by using a Diener Zepto low pressure plasma cleaner.

An image of the custom made setup for the droplet preparation can be seen in Figure 2.4a. The glass substrate served as the base plate of the droplet is placed on a custom-made heating stage attached to micropositioners. In the middle of the heating stage a hole with diameter ~ 10 mm was prepared for the vertical observation. Using a custom made temperature controller system, the temperature of the heating stage could be adjusted up to more than 200 °C with a precision better than 0.1 °C. We used two long distance microscopes to follow the process of

the drop preparation: a Questar QM100 attached to a Canon EOS450D camera for the side view and an Edmund VZM 600I attached to a Hayear HY-500B camera for the vertical view. The droplets were placed on the base plate by a teflon bar (originally a magnetic stirrer) attached to micropositioners. The steps of the droplet preparation were the following: first the liquid crystal was melted on a cleaned glass, then by using the teflon bar we picked-up material by pushing it in the melted compound. The last step was to deposit a droplet on the destination substrate by carefully contacting the picked-up liquid crystal to the substrate. The size of the final droplet depends on the volume of the material on the teflon bar, which can be reduced by making additional droplets on the substrate. In some experiments, the drop had to be precisely placed between electrodes, in which case the position of the drop and the electrodes can be checked through the hole on the heating stage.

We used the setup presented above to determine the contact angle of the sessile droplets on different surfaces. For this, side view snapshots were made, then the surface of the drop was fitted with a circle. The diameter of the drop was determined by using the reflection of the droplet, illustrated in Figure 2.4f. From the diameter of the fitted circle (d_c) and the diameter of the base of the sessile drop (d) the contact angle can be calculated by: $\alpha = \sin^{-1}(d_c/d)$.

In case of the liquid bridge geometry, an additional glass plate was glued on top of the base plate, while the sample was heated up in the N phase. To fix the cell we used Norland Optical Adhesive 61 glue. To control the gap size of the cells we used glass fibre spacers with different sizes.

As a homeotropic alignment layer we used JALS-204 polyimide (JSR, Japan). After the plasma cleaning of the glass plates the thin layer of the polyimide was prepared using spin coating technique: (1) 900 rpm for 9 s and 3000 rpm for 30 s, (2) baking for 30 min at 80 °C and 90 min at 180 °C.

2.4 Photolithography

To produce surface structures, custom electrode geometries and a blocking layer on top of the electrodes with an adjustable thickness, we used photolithography. Photolithography is a widely used microfabrication technique utilizing a photosensitive material known as photoresist, which is typically exposed to UV-light. We used SU8-3000 negative epoxy photoresist from Kayaku Microchem (Japan).

Figure 2.5: Layer thickness of the SU8 insulating layer as a function of the SU8 concentration in cyclopentanone.

We used SU8 layers as alignment and blocking layers to prevent direct charge transfer and electrochemical reactions at the indium-tin-oxide (ITO) transparent electrodes (Chapter 3.2). The SU8 layer provides random planar alignment that can be modified by rubbing. During certain measurements, adjusting the layer thickness was necessary, which is possible by tuning the concentration of SU8-3000 in cyclopentanone. Regardless of the concentration, we used the same preparation method: (1) spin coating on cleaned glass for 7 s at 500 rpm and 30 s at 3000 rpm, by a Polos 150i spin coater. (2) pre-baking for 3 min at 95°C, (3) exposure for 1 min with a UV-LED (at 365 nm), (4) post-baking for 3 min at 95°C, (5) developing for 5 min in SU8 developer, (6) rinsing by isopropanol and drying by air. The dependence of layer thickness as a function of concentration can be seen in Figure 2.5, which was measured by a Veeco Dektak 150 profilometer.

The photolithography method was also used to create patterned surface structures, such as a 850 nm deep circular basin for the experiment discussed in Chapter 3.1 (Figure 3.2). The depth of a structure can be controlled according to Figure 2.5. We used the preparation method as for the homogeneous layers, but with a difference in the pre-baking and post-baking stages. The temperature was ramped up from 65°C to 95°C in one minute, and the sample was then held at 95°C for two minutes. For the 2D patterned structure, the UV exposure was performed by a custom-made UV-laser writing system composed of a Toptica UV-laser (372 nm) with 10x Leica objective and a programmable motorized XY-stage from Standa. Our custom-made controller software written in Labview is able to read g-codes of the designed structure and control the process of the UV laser writing.

Figure 2.6: Schematic drawing of the custom-made setup to study electromechanical effects in FNLCs, with the side-view of the director structure (Schlieren texture) as a result of the absence of the alignment layer. This setup is capable to study both direct and converse piezoelectric responses.

For the custom-made electrodes, first an etching mask was made on top of an ITO-coated glass plate by a $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ thick patterned SU8 layer. After the developing and rinsing steps, we immersed the sample in a 6M hydrochloric acid solution in water for 10 minutes. The acid removed the ITO from the glass, except in areas covered by the SU8 mask. The sample was subsequently washed with deionised water and the SU8 layer was scraped off. The sample was then cleaned again before further processing.

2.5 Electromechanical experiments

Figure 2.6 shows the schematic drawing of the custom made setup designed to investigate electromechanical effects in room temperature FNLCs (Chapter 3.3). The compound is held between two parallel glass plates, coated by ITO conducting layers. The lower glass substrate was fixed in place, and the upper plate was connected to a diaphragm allowing vertical movement, and electrical actuation (which latter was not used in the studies presented). The gap between the glass plates (L) can be adjusted using micro-positioners and measured by using a side view microscope. The upper plate held an accelerometer (Brüer & Kjaer, model BK4375), which was used to determine the vibration amplitude of the sample. A Stanford Research Systems

SR830 lock-in amplifier was used to measure the signal of the accelerometer (U_{acc}) and to produce the driving voltage applied on the sample. The acceleration can be determined by $\Xi = U_{acc}/v_s$, where v_s is the voltage sensitivity (factory calibration factor) of the accelerometer $v_s = 0.61 \text{ mV}/(\text{ms}^{-2})$.

The surface of ITO electrodes was not covered by any alignment or insulating layers, thus application of high voltage could induce electrochemical reactions, which can destroy the sample; consequently, the voltage-dependent measurements were performed in the range between 0-5 V.

We also investigated the electromechanical effects in FNLCs by another experiment, where we carried out electro-acoustic measurements. The sound emitted by the sample was recorded by an IMG Stageline ECM-140 microphone and a Tiepie HS5 oscilloscope. The sound spectra were investigated by Fourier analysis on the amplified signals.

2.6 Finite element calculations

To simulate the structure of the electric field in the investigated geometries we used the COMSOL Multiphysics software. In all simulations, we used the AC/DC - Electric Fields and Currents - Electrostatic - Stationary module. The used equations were: (1) $\nabla \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{0}$ and (2) $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla \phi$, where ϕ is the electric potential.

When we investigated the spontaneous polarisation induced depolarising electric field (Figure 3.3) the electric displacement was: $\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P}_s$, where ε_r is the relative (isotropic) permittivity. When we investigated the structure of the electric field in the liquid bridge geometry (Figure 3.16) the electric displacement was: $\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \mathbf{E}$

Chapter 3: Results and discussion

3.1 Ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal thermo-motor

In this chapter, the behaviour of a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal in the sessile droplet geometry is presented. By analysing the samples near the $N - N_F$ transition temperature in detail, we clarify the evolving director structure and identify the equilibrium polarisation structure in the N_F phase. Additionally, the study unveils temperature gradient-induced flow phenomena, called thermo-motor effect and sheds light on the interplay between thermal gradients and the polarisation structures in sessile droplets. Our primary goal here is to present and characterise the basic phenomena associated with the effect.

3.1.1 Structure of the director field in sessile droplets

During the phase transition of RM734 FNLC from the nematic to the ferroelectric nematic phase the morphology of the director field in sessile droplets significantly change and the new structure forms in two steps. In our studies we wanted to clarify how the director structure of the sessile droplet changes during the transition and what will be the equilibrium state of it in the N_F phase.

The observed POM images of an RM734 sessile droplet with submillimetre diameter are shown in Figure 3.1 at four different temperatures near the nematic-ferroelectric nematic phase transition temperature T_{NN_F} . The structural changes of the drop in cooling can be seen in Supplemental Video 1 of [P1]. The sample was heated from below, resulting in development of a vertical temperature gradient. In the nematic phase, a four-brush texture can be observed with a central defect, as Figure 3.1a shows. The used alignment layer (JALS-204) orients the director to homeotropic in the nematic phase that was verified in an independent measurement using sandwich cells. Based on our previous observations related to sessile droplets [P7], we assumed the director structure presented in Figure 3.1a'-a". The director is perpendicular to the base plate due to the homeotropic alignment and planar with

Figure 3.1: Polarising optical micrographs of a sessile droplet close to the $N \rightarrow N_F$ transition. Temperature at the base plate: T , at the top: $T - \Delta T$. (a) Radial director structure in the N phase ($T - \Delta T > T_{NF}$). (b) Structural change due to the decreasing value of the splay elastic constant close to T_{NF} . (c) The top temperature approaches T_{NF} , which leads to a secondary structural change. (d) The entire drop is in the N_F phase. The primed and double primed figures cross sections of the director structure in side-view and top-view, respectively.

a radial structure at the LC-air interface. For simplicity, we assumed perfect planar director orientation on the upper surface without tilt.

By decreasing the temperature, structural changes can be observed in the droplet structure at around $\sim 2^\circ\text{C}$ above T_{NN_F} as Figure 3.1b shows. The structural changes can be explained by the decreasing value of splay elastic constant K_{11} [21]. On the one hand, at $\sim 2^\circ\text{C}$ above the T_{NN_F} the value of the twist elastic constant (K_{22}) became larger than K_{11} . This may result in a new equilibrium state, as the splay deformation in this region is energetically more favourable. On the other hand, due to the splay deformations the induction of $\mathbf{P}_{fi} = e_1 \mathbf{n}(\nabla \mathbf{n})$ flexoelectric polarisation can be realized. To minimise the contribution to the electrostatic free energy of \mathbf{P}_{fi} , the tangential orientation of the director field became more favourable. By forming tangential structure, the system can prevent the emergence of bound and surface charges. In a sessile droplet the effect starts at the top due to the vertical temperature gradient. The estimated director structure of the droplet in this region can be seen

Figure 3.2: Polarimetric measurements of a thin disc of RM734 to visualise the retardation and the averaged director orientation (green rods) at different temperatures. (a) at $140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the nematic phase, (b) at $134\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ close to $N - N_F$ transition, (c) at $127\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the N_F phase.

in Figure 3.1 b' and b". The temperature range of this stable region is $\sim 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ wide, which is similar for that region where $K_{11} < K_{22}$. [76].

The structure remained stable in cooling until the top of the droplet reached the N_F phase, which induced a secondary structural change, shown in Figure 3.1c. By reaching T_{NN_F} at the top of the drop, spontaneous polarisation (\mathbf{P}_s) is generated. Similarly to the flexoelectric polarisation, the tangential structure of \mathbf{P}_s is energetically more favourable. The value of \mathbf{P}_s starts growing from zero up to $|\mathbf{P}_s| \sim 6\text{ }\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ by decreasing the temperature [23]. In sessile droplets due to the vertical temperature gradient, the tangential structure starts forming at the top of the drop as it reaches the N_F phase; the estimated director structure is presented in Figure 3.1c' and c".

As the droplet cooled further, the whole director structure became tangential except in the vicinity of the central defect as Figure 3.1d' and d" shows. We can estimate the temperature gradient $\sim 23\text{ mK}/\mu\text{m}$, by taking advantage of the temperature difference of the phase transition at the top and at the bottom of the drop by knowing that the height of the drop was $47\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

To verify our assumptions about the director structure, we did polarimetric measurements of RM734 in cylindrical basins of about 850 nm depth. The cylindrical basins were required to decrease the retardation of the sample $\delta < \pi$, where the instrument can give the most reliable results. As a result of the measurement, we can get information about the two dimensional spatial maps of the average director field and the magnitude of optical retardation of the sample. The average director structure is represented by a field of green rods in Figure 3.2. Figure 3.2a shows the

Figure 3.3: Simulation of the electric field in FNLC sessile droplets with three different polarisation structures: (a) tangential, (b) radial and (c) vertical structure. The red arrows illustrate the electric polarisation vector, and the colour map shows the absolute value of the electric field induced by the bound and surface charges. The diameter of the droplets is $d = 200 \mu\text{m}$ with contact angle $\alpha = 40^\circ$. We used parameters $|\mathbf{P}_s| = 6 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $\varepsilon = 10^4$.

radial director structure with a lower value of retardation, due to the homeotropic alignment at the base plate. Close to the transition temperature, the retardation start to increase and the structure start to be spiralling as Figure 3.2b shows. In the N_F phase, the director and thus the spontaneous polarisation field has a tangential structure with a central defect as Figure 3.2c shows. The increased value of the retardation indicates an anchoring transition at the base plate from homeotropic to planar.

As a simple example, we used COMSOL Multiphysics to solve the Poisson equation and to determine the internal electric field in FNLC sessile droplets. We neglected the anisotropy of the material; the used parameters were: $|\mathbf{P}_s| = 6 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $\varepsilon = 10^4$. The calculations were performed using cylindrical coordinate system (z, r, φ) , with the vertical axis of symmetry (z -axis) parallel to the normal vector of the base plate. Figure 3.3 illustrate the distribution of $|\mathbf{E}|$ in sessile droplets with different simplified polarisation structures. The red arrows indicate the polarisation vector, the colour map shows the absolute value of \mathbf{E} . Figure 3.3b and Figure 3.3c indicate strong internal electric fields when the polarisation has only vertical and radial components, respectively. In contrast, when the polarisation was set to tangential (Figure 3.3a) the absolute value of \mathbf{E} is mostly about zero, except in the vicinity of the central defect. We can understand this result by considering that the sources of the internal electric field are the surface charges that emerge when \mathbf{P}_s has a non-zero component along the surface normal at a boundary. In the case of

Figure 3.4: (a)-(d) Snapshots of an RM734 sessile droplet (at 131 °C in the ferroelectric nematic phase) taken in time series in a polarising microscope with crossed polarisers and a lambda plate. The two arrows indicate two groups of tracer particles following a circular orbit around a central defect. (e) Angular velocity of the tracers as a function of the temperature. (f) Snapshot of a sessile droplet with two defects at the upper surface (marked by yellow dots). Around the defects flow with opposite direction can be observed (marked by red arrows).

the tangential polarisation field, such surface charges are absent in contrast to the radial and vertical case, where the internal electric field can be well approximated by the expression of the depolarising electric field $\mathbf{E} = -\frac{\mathbf{P}_s}{\epsilon_0\epsilon}$.

These results support our assumption that the minimal electric energy corresponds to the tangential configuration, which is supported by our experimental findings.

3.1.2 Temperature gradient induced flow

During the preparation of the sessile droplets, micron sized impurities (dust particles) can be found in the material. These particles are in rest in the N phase, but after the transition to the N_F phase they start to move in a circular path around the central defect core at the top surface of the drop. For further characterization of the flow, we intentionally doped the liquid crystal by $8\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter polystyrene microspheres (from Sigma-Aldrich) for tracers. Time series snapshots of the orbiting flow are presented in Figure 3.4a-d, where the yellow and green arrows point to two

clusters of the tracers. Supplemental Video 2 of [P1] shows the orbiting motion of clusters. Besides the tracers we could also observe the circular motion of defect lines inside larger droplets (Supplemental Video 5 of [P1]), which indicates stationary rotational flow without continuous director rotation.

We noticed that the velocity of the circulating motion close to the phase transition is slower than in the deep ferroelectric nematic state. To verify our observation, we measured the angular velocity of the impurities as a function of the temperature. The detailed description of the evaluation method to measure the angular velocity of the tracers can be seen in the Appendix (A.1). The results can be seen in Figure 3.4e. The measured angular velocity increases sharply below the phase transition and it seems to saturate about 3 °C below T_{NNF} , however, a small maximum is observed at $T - T_{NNF} \sim -5$ °C.

The direction of the circulation can be different drop by drop and in some drops, we also observed that it can be reversed after heating to the nematic phase and cooling back. The centre of the circulation is always the defect core at the upper surface. Figure 3.4f and Supplemental Video 4 of [P1] show a large droplet of RM734, with two defect cores at the top surface. Around the two defects, circulating flow with opposite direction can be observed (the directions of the circulations are indicated by red arrows).

When we opened the lid of the heating stage or cooled the upper part of the droplet by air, the flow velocity increased. We conducted measurements where we altered the temperature gradient direction by flipping the cell upside down or by heating the sample from the top instead of from the bottom. We observed that reversing the temperature gradient direction also reverses the direction of the flow and it can be even stopped by setting the same temperature at the bottom and at the top of the drop (Supplemental Video 3 of [P1]). Based on the observations, we concluded that the temperature gradient has a key role in the phenomena.

Further experiments showed that electric field applied by in-plane surface electrodes (placed one millimetre apart) can affect the position of the defect core at the top surface of the droplet. In the nematic phase, the defect moved along parallel directions to the electric fields at low frequency ($f < 1$ Hz) AC or DC fields. By increasing the amplitude of the fields, the development of a defect wall parallel to the electrodes was observed regardless of the frequency, as previously observed in nematic sessile droplets [P8], [P9], [P10]. The displacement of the defect in the

Figure 3.5: In-plane DC electric field induced displacement of the central defect core (indicated by coloured dots) subjected to ± 50 V in the case of two droplets: with (a) clockwise and (b) counterclockwise flow.

ferroelectric nematic phase is shown in Figure 3.5, where the defects were displaced at an angle of 45° to the external electric field rather than parallel; the direction of the displacement depends on the direction of the flow. Our experiments indicated negative charge accumulation in the defects in case of the observed droplets shown in Figure 3.5a-b, independently from the direction of the flow. We also measured the displacement of the defect after we reversed the direction of the temperature gradient and we found that the displacement is independent of the direction of the temperature gradient. This indicates that the charge of the defects is not induced by pyroelectricity due to the vertical temperature gradient.

Based on the experimental facts, it can be stated that the driving force behind the flow is the temperature gradient. In the polar nematic phase, cross effects, like thermohydrodynamic coupling were predicted theoretically [77], but the specific physical mechanisms and the experimental significance have not been clarified yet. The presence of the temperature gradient gives rise to pyroelectric effects that can induce bound charges in the samples. In our paper related to this study [P1] based on the primary results, we suggested an explanation based on an electrostatic driving force of the effect originating from pyroelectric charges. However, the proposed theoretical description is not compatible with our latest results namely the temperature dependence of the flow velocity and the structure of the depolarising electric fields in sessile droplets. For a more precise description of the phenomenon, further experiments and simulations are necessary.

3.1.3 Summary and outlook

In Chapter 3.1, we presented a new, extraordinary phenomenon called thermo-motor effect observed in ferroelectric nematics, where the presence of temperature gradient induces material flow. The effect can be observed exclusively in the N_F polar phase. First, we investigated the director and polarisation structures in sessile droplets. We proved that the polarisation tends to form a tangential structure in ferroelectric nematic sessile droplets, which can be explained by the minimisation of the electrostatic free energy. Similar tangential structures were found in other FNLCs with direct isotropic- N_F transition, when the droplets are in their isotropic melt [78, 79] and in DIO and RM734 conical domains [80]. We presented the basic observations related to the thermo-motor effect and we showed that the temperature gradient has a key role in the mechanism. Our primary consideration was the presentation of the effect. For a more detailed understanding, we plan to conduct further experiments and simulations. We will investigate the effect in sandwich cell geometry with various combination of temperature gradients and polarisation directions.

We note that we observed the thermo-motor effect in other FNLCs also, indicating it is a general phenomenon in ferroelectric liquids. Since the effect is observable only in the N_F phase and a small amount of material is sufficient for preparing a sessile droplet, the phenomenon can be well used to indicate the N_F phase in the case of new possible FNLC materials.

3.2 Electric field induced surface instabilities

In this chapter, we reveal the nature of two AC electric field induced surface instability that we observed in ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals in sessile drop and in liquid bridge geometry. The primary instability that we could observe in both geometries is called ramification. The other instability found only in the liquid bridge geometry at higher voltages compared to the ramification is called labyrinthine instability. Our aim was to characterise both effects by systematically changing the experimental parameters. First, we present our results related to the sessile droplet geometry, in which we investigated the ramification instability by using various electrode structures. Later, we analyse the surface instabilities in the liquid bridge geometry. Finally, we present a new type of self-propelled system of FNLC droplets that we observed in the liquid bridge geometry. In our experiments, we investigated the RM734 compound. All measurements were done at 5 °C below the $N \rightarrow N_F$ phase transition unless it is indicated differently.

3.2.1 Ramification instability of sessile droplets

First, we studied the effect of AC electric field in the sessile droplet geometry in a vertical electric field. The experimental geometry is presented in Figure 3.6a. The gap between the bounding substrates was 150 μm and the ITO electrodes were covered by 1.4 μm thick blocking layer. The POM snapshots at voltage $U = 210$ V, 220 V and 300 V (at frequency $f = 10$ kHz) can be seen in Figure 3.6 b-d. As we increased the applied voltage, we could not observe any change in the structure of the sessile droplet until reaching 210 V. Above that voltage we observed the ejection of jets starting to spread on the surface of the electrodes. Some of the jets were decorated by additional secondary jets. After the ejection of the jets strong convection could be observed inside the droplet. The jets remained stable as long as the field was turned on and they became thicker and longer as we increased the voltage. When we switched off the electric field, the material started to flow back to the initial droplet shape and the jets disappeared. The emergence of the branches can be seen also in Supplemental Video 1 of [P2].

Unfortunately, for further characterisation this geometry was not appropriate, because of the voltage attenuation between the air and the LC. The value of the

Figure 3.6: Ramification instability induced by electric fields applied along the normal direction of the base plate in a ferroelectric nematic sessile droplet. (a) Schematic drawing of the geometry with approximated fringing electric field (green lines) and coordinate system. (b-d) Polarising optical microscopy images of a sessile droplet in the N_F phase, between crossed polarisers and a full-wave plate at 210 V, 220 V and 300 V, respectively. The cell gap was $L = 150 \mu\text{m}$ and the electrodes were covered by $L_i = 1.4 \mu\text{m}$ thick blocking layers.

electric field in the material highly depends on the height of the drop, as a result it is difficult to compare different samples. The sessile droplet geometry is not stable, since at high voltages the electric field pulls the droplet to the top electrode creating a stable liquid bridge, which remains even after switching the voltage off.

Figure 3.7 presents the schematics of the in-plane electrode configurations, accompanied by snapshots capturing ferroelectric nematic droplets. In Figure 3.7a the structure of the interdigitated electrodes and the used coordinate system are depicted. Figures 3.7b and 3.7c present side views ($x - z$ plane) of the electrodes showing the fringing field and the sessile droplet, respectively. The width of the electrodes and the gap between them were $10 \mu\text{m}$ and the surface of the substrate was covered by a $1.4 \mu\text{m}$ thick insulating layer. The top-view ($x - y$ plane) reflection microscopy image of a droplet at zero voltage can be seen in Figure 3.7d. The recorded video of the instability can be seen in Supplemental Video 3 of [P2] at $f = 10 \text{ kHz}$, when we increased then decreased the applied voltage. Figure 3.7e illustrates the same droplet under an applied voltage ($f = 10 \text{ kHz}$, $U = 75 \text{ V}$), above the threshold of the ramification instability, where the emergence of the branched fingers are clearly observable. The branches grow solely on the bright stripes corresponding to the electrode areas. Figure 3.7f presents a side view of the case, where the gap between electrodes ($180 \mu\text{m}$) is significantly larger than the electrode width ($10 \mu\text{m}$). Figure 3.7g provides the corresponding POM snapshot of the sessile droplet above the instability threshold. The image distinctly reveals that the branches are located on the top of the electrodes, where the electric field has mainly vertical component.

Figure 3.7: Illustration of the in-plane electrode geometry and micrographs of the ferroelectric nematic droplet on surface electrodes. (a): Schematic drawing of the interdigitated electrodes with the used coordinate system. Side view ($x - z$ plane) of the electrodes (b) with fringing field and (c) the sessile droplet. Reflection microscopy image ($x - y$ plane) of the droplet at (d) 0 V and (e) 75 V applied voltage at $f = 10$ kHz. Brighter stripes correspond to the electrode areas; the electrode distance was $10 \mu\text{m}$. (f) Side view of the geometry with a single thin pair of electrodes with a larger gap ($180 \mu\text{m}$) between them. (g) The corresponding polarising microscope image, showing that the fluid fingers spread above the electrodes, where the fringing field is perpendicular to the substrate.

The emergence of the branches in the interdigitated electrode geometry was less explosive, more controllable and reproducible, which allowed more detailed study of the instability. To characterise the instability, we used the perimeter of the droplet as an indicator, because it increased significantly due to the fractal-like tips. To measure the perimeter of the droplets first, the images were Fourier transformed and the peaks corresponding to the periodic electrode stripes were masked. Then, the image was Fourier transformed again, resulting in a homogeneous background that is suitable for further image processing. The perimeter of the droplets were measured by using a custom-made evaluation program (see Appendix (A.2)) based on contour finding method available in the OpenCV Python package [81]. To determine the threshold voltage of the instability (U_{Ri}), the perimeter was measured as a function of the voltage (Figure 3.8a) and the data was fitted with the function:

$$\mathcal{F}(U) = a \cdot \ln(1 + e^{b \cdot (U - U_{th})}) + c, \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.8: (a) The normalised perimeter of the droplet (C_i/C_{i0}) in the in-plane electrode geometry as a function of the applied voltage at $f = 10$ kHz. C_{i0} is the perimeter of the droplet at $U = 0$ V. (b) The threshold voltage of the ramification instability in in-plane electrode geometry (U_{Ri}) as a function of temperature at $f = 1$ kHz. (c) The normalised perimeter of a $125 \mu\text{m}$ diameter droplet as a function of temperature under constant applied voltage ($U = 75$ V, $f = 10$ kHz). (d) U_{Ri} as a function of frequency.

where U_{th} is the threshold voltage and, a , b and c are further fitting parameters [82].

Figure 3.8b illustrates the temperature dependence of the threshold voltage at $f = 1$ kHz. The red line indicates the nematic to ferroelectric nematic phase transition temperature (T_{NNF}) determined at $U = 0$ V. We note that the presence of an electric field can shift the transition temperature to the N_F phase according to Szydłowska et al. [83]. In the deep N_F phase, the threshold voltage remains nearly constant, and it starts to increase closer to T_{NNF} . We could observe the instability even in the N phase as far as 8 °C above the T_{NNF} , but the required threshold voltage increased rapidly further from the transition temperature. In the N phase, the effect is weaker, the branches are shorter at a given voltage than in the N_F phase. To characterise the differences in the N and N_F , we cooled the sample from isotropic phase to the N_F phase at a constant $U = 70$ V applied voltage with $f = 10$ kHz and measured the normalised circumference (C_i/C_{i0}) of the droplet, where C_{i0} is the circumference of the drop at zero applied voltage. The result can be seen in Figure 3.8c. The value of C_i/C_{i0} remains near one in the isotropic and in the higher

Figure 3.9: (a) A sessile droplet in the wide in-plane electrode geometry. Polarising optical microscopy images of ferroelectric nematic droplets on surface electrode pairs (with $180\ \mu\text{m}$ gap) (b) at 0 V, (c) at 90 V and (d) at 120 V with $f = 500$ Hz sinusoidal driving voltage. (e) A series of neighbouring droplets showing ramification and repulsive interaction. (f) A magnified area near two branches showing that the tips arrange to avoid contact between neighbour tips.

temperature nematic range, but it starts to increase sharply already in the N phase before entering to the N_F phase.

In Figure 3.8d, we depict the frequency dependence of U_{Ri} in the N_F phase. Across the frequency range of $f = 100$ Hz–100 kHz, the minimum threshold is measured at around 1 kHz. Notably, the threshold voltage exhibits a sharp increase towards both the lower and higher extremes of the examined frequency range, which can be explained by the fact that at low frequency the screening ability of the ions becomes more significant, while at high frequency the polarisation can no longer follow entirely the electric field.

Motivated by the observation that the ramification occurs on top of the electrodes, we created a sample depicted in Figure 3.9a, where the width of the electrodes was significantly larger than the gap between them ($180\ \mu\text{m}$). Figure 3.9b-f show the POM snapshots of the branched structures induced by the applied voltage. As the voltage rises in the wide-electrode geometry, the droplet begins to spread onto the area of the electrodes, where the z -component of the electric field is dominant. Above the threshold voltage of the instability, strong convection can be observed both inside

the droplet and in the branches. As the droplet spreads, multiple branches emerge, forming a fractal-like structure as shown in Figure 3.9c. The effect becomes stronger above 90 V, beyond which the droplet spreads parallel to the electrodes, as shown in Figure 3.9d. By increasing the applied voltages, the droplet expands further along the electrodes and elongates. It is crucial to note that the branched structure remains unchanged over time as long as the applied voltage remains constant.

When multiple droplets are deposited in a line, we observed in case of a well-developed instability that the droplets repelled each other instead of merging, as Figure 3.9e depicts. Further examination of the POM images taken with a full-wave plate revealed the molecular arrangement within the branches. In Figure 3.9f, the blue and orange tips indicate parallel and perpendicular orientation of the director with respect to the full-wave plate axis, respectively. This observation suggests that, the director and thus the spontaneous polarisation are aligned along the branches, which explains the electrostatic nature of the repulsion between neighbouring fingers.

For the well-developed branched structure shown in Figure 3.9c, we calculated the Hausdorff or fractal dimension (\mathbb{H}) by using image analysis based on the box counting algorithm [84] implemented in the PoreSpy module of Python [85]. We obtained $\mathbb{H} = 1.61 \pm 0.1$, which indeed yields a fractal nature of the structure since $\mathbb{H} < 2$.

We conducted polarimetric microscopy measurements to analyse the director arrangement of the branched structure. The result is shown in Figure 3.10a, where the map of the green rods represents the average director orientation field in the sample plane. The map verifies our previous observation that the director aligns parallel to the branches, resulting in bound charges at the tips that repel each other.

For further investigation, the sample in the N_F phase was quenched by suddenly dropping it into liquid nitrogen while the electric field was applied on it. Rapid solidification preserved some of the branched structure of the ferroelectric nematic fluid. However, we suspect though, that some of the even finer structures may have destroyed during the quenching process.

Figure 3.10b shows the surface topography of the branched structure in a quenched crystallised sample, measured by using a white light interferometric profilometer. The colour-coded height profile was calculated from the flat base substrate. The inset of Figure 3.10b illustrates the cross section of one finger from the low-

Figure 3.10: Morphology of the fluid branches induced by the ramification instability in a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal sessile droplet in the wide-electrode geometry. (a) Polarimetric microscopy image, where the green rods indicate the effective orientation of the director. (b) Surface topography of the branched structure measured by interferometric profilometry. The inset shows the cross-section of one branch indicated by a dotted grey line. (c) Scanning electron microscopy image of a crystallised, quenched sample. The scanning electron microscopy image was taken by László Péter.

est level of the hierarchy along the dashed line in Figure 3.10b. The dimensions of the finger were found to be approximately $2 \mu\text{m}$ in width and $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in height, approaching the resolution limit of our optical microscopy techniques.

To get more details on the fine structure and tip dimensions of the electric field-induced fingers, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was applied on quenched samples. The SEM micrographs were recorded by László Péter (Wigner Research Centre for Physics) using a TESCAN MIRA3 scanning electron microscope equipped with a field-emission gun. Figure 3.10c displays a representative SEM image, revealing the branched structure with finer details. The magnified view of a selected tip in Figure 3.10c highlights submicron radius of curvature ($\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) at the end of the finger. We note that both profilometry and SEM experiments were conducted on the same area of the same sample.

3.2.2 Ramification and labyrinthine instability in liquid bridges

The liquid bridge geometry shown in Figure 3.11a has been thoroughly investigated as part of our research. In this configuration, the FNLC was positioned between two parallel ITO coated glass substrates. The inner surfaces of the electrodes were coated by insulating (blocking) layers (indicated by the green layers in Figure 3.11a).

Figure 3.11a'-c" show the typical response of a ferroelectric nematic in the liquid bridge geometry, when sinusoidal AC electric field with $f = 1$ kHz is applied. Figure 3.11a-c show the schematic illustration of a liquid bridge's morphology in different ranges of the applied voltage. In absence of an external electric field, the liquid bridge takes the form of a hyperboloid of one sheet, as seen in Figure 3.11a. Given that the contact angle of the used FNLC (RM734) on the blocking layer (SU8) is typically ranging between 35° - 45° , the LC-air interface exhibits curvature, resulting in a concave meniscus. In the microscopy images, the meniscus manifests as a black circle in the basic state ($U = 0$ V) of the bridge, as depicted in Figure 3.11a'. The dark appearance is attributed to the refraction of light on the curved meniscus; the corresponding contour line is denoted as the meniscus line. It is crucial to distinguish the meniscus line from the contact line, which represents the interface between the air and the liquid crystal on the solid substrate.

Upon applying a sufficiently high AC voltage to the cell, the ramification instability initiates at a threshold voltage (U_R). The emergence of the ramification instability in the liquid bridge geometry is shown in Supplemental Video 2 of [P2] at $f = 10$ kHz. The primary instability occurs along the contact line, while the meniscus line remains unaltered, as seen in Figure 3.11b'. Figure 3.11d shows the snapshot of a different sample from side view. It can be clearly seen that the fingers induced by the ramification instability are located in the vicinity of the base substrate. If the voltage is increased further, the growth of the branches continues until a certain critical voltage (U_L) is reached, when another instability occurs. During this secondary instability, the entire meniscus line undergoes a sudden morphological transition; the initial circular shape becomes unstable and it starts to deform, as depicted in Figure 3.11c'. At even higher voltages, illustrated in Figure 3.11c",

Figure 3.11: Structure of the liquid bridge geometry and the used coordinate system (a). The liquid crystal is between two ITO coated glass plates covered by L_i thick insulating layers. The gap between the substrates is L . The schematic illustration and micrographs of the ferroelectric nematic sample: (a-a') without electric field applied, (b-b') above the U_R threshold of the ramification and (c-c'') above the U_L threshold of the labyrinthine instability. The AC voltage was switched between the bounding plates, thus far from the bridges the electric field is parallel to the z -direction. Snapshot (c') represents the state slightly above the threshold field of the labyrinthine instability, while (c'') shows the morphology at higher voltage. The meniscus line of the liquid bridge (black circles in (a') and in (b') and black curves in (c') and in (c'')) is affected only by the secondary, labyrinthine instability. (d) Side view of a different sample at a voltage where only the primary, ramification instability is emerged. The snapshot clearly indicates that the tips are formed in the vicinity of the electrodes. The schematic illustration describes the experiment for side-view imaging using a long-range microscope.

the meniscus line takes a complex structure, prompting us to term this secondary morphological transition of the liquid bridge as the labyrinthine instability.

To determine the threshold voltage of the primary ramification instability (U_R) in liquid bridge geometry and to precisely analyse the voltage dependence of it, a geometric transformation was employed, wherein the contact line was mapped onto a straight line as Figure 3.12a-c shows. The transformation process involved fitting the undeformed drop with an ellipsoid, followed by re-plotting the images in the new

Figure 3.12: Steps of image processing to determine the threshold voltages and to characterise the instabilities. For the ramification instability, (a) first we fit the undeformed droplet by an ellipse. (b) The ramification instability induced branches around the meniscus line and the new coordinate system. (c) The vicinity of the meniscus line was replotted in the new (r, φ) coordinate system. In case of the labyrinthine instability, the contour of the meniscus line can be easily detected by a contour finding method, due to the sharp contrast. (d) Image of maze-like structure of the droplet. (e) Binary image (purple-green) after the image processing; the outer contour of the meniscus line is indicated by yellow colour.

coordinate system according to (r, φ) . We defined the roughness of the contact line as:

$$Ro_{cl} = \sum_{\varphi} \left| \partial_{\varphi}^2 \sum_r \mathcal{I}(r, \varphi) \right|, \quad (3.2)$$

where $\mathcal{I}(r, \varphi)$ is the intensity map of the transformed image (Figure 3.12c) as a function of the radius r and the azimuthal angle φ . ∂_{φ}^2 denotes the second derivative with respect to φ . The threshold voltage can be calculated from the voltage dependence of Ro_{cl} by fitting it with the $\mathcal{F}(U)$ function according to Eq. (3.1). The main steps of the image processing can be found in the Appendix (A.3)

Determining the U_L threshold voltage is simpler for the secondary labyrinthine instability. The meniscus line is consistently black in the images, allowing to be easily identified using a contour finding method (see Appendix (A.4)). The advantage of

Figure 3.13: (a) The roughness of the contact line (Ro_{cl}) of the fluid bridge as a function of the applied voltage at $f = 1$ kHz. (b) normalised length of the meniscus line (S/S_0) as a function of the applied voltage at $f = 1$ kHz. S_0 is the length of the meniscus line at 0 V. The threshold voltage of the ramification instability (U_R) is also marked on the graph. The inset shows the time dependence of S/S_0 after switching on the voltage from zero to 60 V (blue), 65 V (red), 70 V (green). Threshold voltages of the instabilities as a function of the (c) temperature at $f = 1$ kHz and (d) frequency. The cell parameters were: $L \approx 15 \mu\text{m}$ and $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$.

the process is the insensitivity to the branching instability as demonstrated in Figure 3.12d-e. As the deformation of the meniscus line results in a significant increase in its length, it can be used to characterise the labyrinthine instability.

The roughness of the contact line (Ro_{cl}) as a function of the voltage at $f = 1$ kHz is presented in Figure 3.13a. By increasing the voltage, the value of Ro_{cl} remains constant up to 42 V, when it starts to sharply increase due to the emerging ramification instability. Similar behaviour can be observed by decreasing the voltage with a slightly lower threshold at 38 V. This hysteresis indicates a weakly first order nature of the instability.

Figure 3.13b shows the normalised length of the meniscus line (S/S_0) as a function of the voltage, where S_0 is the length of the meniscus line at 0 V. The value of S/S_0 sharply increases above $U_L = 82$ V when we increased the voltage. By decreasing the voltage, S/S_0 became one at around 71 V. Besides the first order nature, this relatively wide hysteresis can also be explained by the fact that the labyrinthine instability requires usually long time to reach the stationary state. The time dependence of S/S_0 after switching the voltage from zero ($t = 0$ s) to 60 V, 65 V and 70 V at $f = 1$ kHz can be seen in the inset of Figure 3.13b. When the voltage was raised to 60 V, slightly below the threshold voltage, the drop's shape changed after 40 seconds.

The temperature and frequency dependence of both instabilities are depicted in Figure 3.13c and 3.13d, respectively. We observed qualitatively similar behaviour in both instabilities compared to the interdigitated electrode geometry. Both instabilities emerged even in the nematic phase, although the required threshold voltages sharply increased. When examining the dependence on frequency, it is notable that the minimum threshold voltage occurs at approximately 1 kHz, with an increase evident at both lower and higher frequency ranges, similarly to our finding in the in-plane geometry (Figure 3.8). The qualitative explanation for the minimum thresholds at the intermediate frequency range holds here as well. At lower frequencies, the screening effect of ionic mobile charges becomes stronger, while at higher frequencies, the effective magnitude of the spontaneous polarisation decreases, because of the finite speed of polarisation reorientation in the AC field, which is hindered by viscous dissipation.

During our investigations, we identified the substantial influence of the insulating layer thickness on both the ramification and labyrinthine instabilities. Measurements were conducted using cells without blocking layers, allowing direct contact between the liquid crystal and the conducting ITO layers. Remarkably, neither the ramification nor the labyrinthine instability was observed under these conditions. To

Figure 3.14: (a) The threshold voltages of the ramification (U_R) and the labyrinthine instability (U_L) as a function of the insulating layers' thickness (L_i). The green data points correspond to a cell with different L_i (260 nm and 5788 nm) on the two sides. The average of the two values was used for the placement of the data points on the horizontal axis. In the mixed cell, the long branches emerge only on the side with the thicker blocking layer. (b) Length of the longest branch as a function of L_i recorded at $U = 1.3 \cdot U_R$. The gap sizes of the cells were in the range 12 μm -20 μm . Snapshots of the ramification instability in cells with different blocking layer thickness: (c) 51 nm, (d) 750 nm and (e) 5788 nm ($f = 1$ kHz). The appearance of droplets at $U = 1.3 \cdot U_L$ above the threshold of the labyrinthine instability driven at $f = 1$ kHz with (f) 51 nm, (g) 315 nm and (h) 2966 nm blocking layer thicknesses.

examine the impact of the insulating layer on the appearance of ramification and labyrinthine instabilities, a systematic study was carried out by changing the insulating layer thickness ranging from 51 nm to up to 5788 nm.

Figure 3.14a displays how the voltage thresholds (U_R and U_L) depend on the thickness of the insulating layer. The gap size of the cells was $L \approx 15 \mu\text{m}$. We observed that higher voltages are required to induce the instabilities with thicker insulating layers due to the voltage attenuation between the LC and blocking layers. Figure 3.14b shows that the length of the branches for the ramification instability strongly depends on the thickness of the blocking layer. For the thinnest blocking layer (~ 51 nm), the branches were approximately $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ in length, as shown in

Figure 3.15: (a) Threshold voltage of the labyrinthine (U_L) and the ramification (U_R) instability as a function of the gap size L . The electrodes were coated by $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick insulating layers. (b) Threshold voltage of the labyrinthine instability (U_L) as a function of the initial radius of the liquid bridges' bases driven at $f = 1 \text{ kHz}$ with $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ blocking layers and $12.4 \mu\text{m}$ gap.

Figure 3.14c. Conversely, when the blocking layer was $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$, the branch length exceeded $100 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Figure 3.14e.

When cells possessed identical blocking layer thickness (L_i) on both sides, branches exhibit similar lengths on both sides. Additionally, we constructed a 'mixed' cell with different L_i on the opposite substrates, 5788 nm on one side and 260 nm on the other. In Figure 3.14a for the 'mixed' cell, the average of the two L_i values was used for the placement of the green data points on the horizontal (L_i) axis. In the 'mixed' cell, the long branches could be observed only on the side, which is covered by the thicker blocking layer as presented in the inset of Figure 3.14a. Note that the threshold voltage for the 'mixed' cell is almost the same as that of the uniform L_i case, if L_i for the mixed cell corresponds to the average of the layer thicknesses on the two sides.

The ramification instability consistently emerges at lower voltages than the labyrinthine instability, making it challenging to characterise the labyrinthine instability independently. We observed that the morphology of the labyrinthine instability is less sensitive to the blocking layer thickness compared to the ramification. Figures 3.14f-h depict liquid bridges undergone the labyrinthine instability at $U = 1.3 \cdot U_L$ and $f = 1 \text{ kHz}$ with increasing values of blocking layer thickness. It is evident that the closed loops of the meniscus lines (dark curves) are separated due to the repulsion between the branches generated by the ramification. With increasing L_i resulting in longer branches, the labyrinthine structure becomes sparser.

We examined the behaviour of the instabilities in cells with different gap sizes (L). Our goal during sample preparation was to maintain preferably identical liquid bridge diameters within the cells. The blocking layers' thickness remained constant at $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. For both instabilities, it was observed that the threshold voltages increased for low L and subsequently decreased sharply to about $L \sim 15 \mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 3.15a). The dependence of the threshold voltages on the gap size began to flatten towards higher values of L . A slight increase in U_L was observed at the upper range of the gap studied, although there was no significant change in the threshold of ramification.

During the experiment, it was noted that the application of voltages higher than U_L results in the disintegration of the labyrinthine structure into smaller pieces. Another way to achieve this fragmentation is by immediately switching off the voltage in the case of a well-developed labyrinthine structure. We noticed that the threshold voltage of the liquid bridges with smaller size is increased by repeating the fragmentation process several times. Figure 3.15b shows the size dependence of U_L at $f = 1 \text{ kHz}$, with $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $L = 12.4 \mu\text{m}$. We observed that U_L increases for liquid bridges with smaller size, however, we did not detect this behaviour for the threshold voltage of the ramification instability.

We emphasize that the presence of an insulating layer on the electrodes is a requirement for both interfacial instabilities. The thickness of the insulating layer significantly affects both the threshold voltages and the morphology of the instabilities. To provide a clearer understanding, we used COMSOL Multiphysics to solve the Poisson equation and simulate the electric field distribution in the liquid bridge geometry.

Figure 3.16a shows the schematic of the studied geometry and the parameters. Our simulations model the liquid bridge as a hyperboloid of one sheet with predefined thickness (L) and contact angle (α). The liquid bridge is positioned between two planar insulator sheets of thickness L_i (marked as green in Figure 3.16a). We consider air as a third medium outside the liquid crystal and between the insulating layers. We considered cylindrical symmetry and utilized cylindrical (r, φ, z) coordinates, which means that the symmetry axis is oriented along the z -direction. In the simulations, constant electric potentials were prescribed as $\phi(z = +L/2 + L_i) = -U/2$ and $\phi(z = -L/2 - L_i) = +U/2$, on the top and the bottom electrodes. The liquid bridge had a base radius of $R_0 = 50 \mu\text{m}$, while the insulating layers and the

electrodes had a radius of $R_\infty = 100 \mu\text{m}$. For simplicity, our model is isotropic, we have disregarded anisotropy and spontaneous polarisation of the liquid crystal. In the simulations, the relative permittivity of the air was $\varepsilon_{air} = 1$ while that of the insulating layer was $\varepsilon_i = 4$. The ferroelectric nature of the liquid crystal has been taken into account by considering a huge relative permittivity, $\varepsilon_{LC} = 10000$. To achieve optimal computational efficiency without compromising the results, the simulated volume and mesh sizes were systematically adjusted. The parameters were selected by ensuring that the outcomes near the contact line remained unaffected. Additionally, we constrained the maximum mesh size within the liquid crystal to 100 nm. It is important to emphasise that our simplified model did not aim to provide a perfect representation of the phenomena under investigation, rather, its main purpose was to explain critical qualitative aspects. Taking into account anisotropy, orientational elasticity bound to the spontaneous polarisation field of the liquid crystal, and the inclusion of AC voltage driving with dissipative director dynamics, and covering ionic conductivity in the simulation were beyond the scope of this study. Such improvements remain possible areas for further research.

The electric field in a dielectric liquid between two insulating layers, when the fluid entirely fills the cell or far from the liquid-air interface can be determined analytically. The electric field has only z -component with magnitude:

$$E_0 = U(2L_i \frac{\varepsilon_{LC}}{\varepsilon_i} + L)^{-1} \quad (3.3)$$

As a consequence, if $\varepsilon_{LC} \gg \varepsilon_i$, the strong reduction of the electric field occurs inside the liquid crystal is expected.

When the liquid crystal partially fills the cell, the electric field cannot be calculated easily close to the (triple) junction of LC-air-insulating layer. For numerical simulation of the problem, we used COMSOL Multiphysics to determine the distribution of the $\mathbf{E} = (E_r, E_\varphi, E_z)$ electric field in the sample. The structure of the electric field is shown in Figure 3.16b and Figure 3.16c without and with insulating layers between the LC and the electrodes, respectively. The normalised electric field (\mathbf{E}/E_0) is represented by white arrows and the value of $|\mathbf{E}/E_0|$ is displayed on the colour map. When we set $L_i = 0$ (Figure 3.16b), the LC is in direct contact with the electrodes, thus the electric field has to be along the z axis at the top and bottom boundaries. In the central part of the LC, the field has only vertical component, but

Figure 3.16: (a) The schematic drawing and the parameters of the simulated geometry. The parameters: L_i -insulating layer thickness, L -cell gap, R_0 -base radius of the liquid bridge, α contact angle and ϵ_{LC} , ϵ_i , ϵ_{air} the relative permittivity of liquid crystal, insulating layer and air. Distribution and magnitude of the electric field in the liquid bridge calculated by COMSOL Multiphysics: (b) $L_i = 0$ and (c) $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$. The arrows and the colour-map show the normalised electric field ($|\mathbf{E}/E_0|$). The gap was $L = 20 \mu\text{m}$ with $\alpha = 35^\circ$.

close to the LC-air interface, due to the curvature of the meniscus, \mathbf{E} has also a small radial component. Further from the meniscus $|\mathbf{E}/E_0| \approx 1$, but closer to the triple junction, the magnitude of the field decreases. In contrast, when the electrodes were covered by $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick insulating layers, the structure of the electric field entirely changed, as Figure 3.16c shows. Near the meniscus, the magnitude of the field significantly increased and a strong radial electric field component emerged close to the triple junction. In the deep bulk part, similarly, \mathbf{E} has only vertical component and the value of $|\mathbf{E}/E_0|$ decreases to ≈ 1 .

The absolute value and radial component of the normalised electric field, plotted against the z -coordinate on a curved line at 100 nm, 200 nm and 300 nm distance from the meniscus, are shown in Figure 3.17. The data were normalised by E_0 introduced in Eq. 3.3. Both the magnitude and radial component of the electric field increase closer to the bounding plates, which corresponds with our previous

Figure 3.17: (a) Absolute value of the normalised electric field ($|\mathbf{E}/E_0|$) and (b) the normalised radial component of the electric field E_r/E_0 in the liquid bridge along the curved meniscus (indicated by dashed line in the inset) at 100 nm, 200 nm, and 300 nm distance from the air interface plotted versus the z -coordinate. The blocking layer was $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick and the gap was $20 \mu\text{m}$, with contact angle 35° .

observations that the ramification occurs close to the electrode surface (see Figure 3.11). Furthermore, the direction of the radial electric field component is the opposite at the bottom and the top of the liquid bridge. The sign of E_r is reversed if we change the polarity of the applied voltage.

To compare the simulated and measured data, we computed the radial component of the electric field (E_{r-ref}) at the junction of the three media for the cell with $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $L = 15 \mu\text{m}$ at a voltage of 53.4 V. This voltage is consistent with the threshold voltage of the ramification instability in a cell with the same parameters. The E_{r-ref} field was then taken as the reference value for the threshold electric field. In the simulation, the gap size and insulating layer thickness of the cell were systematically varied. Subsequently, the voltage (denoted by U_{R-sim}) was adjusted to achieve the reference E_{r-ref} electric field value. Figure 3.18 illustrates the dependence of U_{R-sim} on the layer thickness and gap size, as determined from the E_{r-ref} reference field. The simulated data (U_{R-sim} - marked by blue colour in Figure 3.18) exhibit similar dependence as the measured data (U_R - marked by red colour in Figure 3.18). The coincidence of the measured and simulated data indicates that the origin of the ramification instability is indeed from the presence of radial electric field because of the insulating layer.

Figure 3.18c shows the layer thickness dependence of the normalised radial electric field ($|E_r/E_0|$). The value of $|E_r/E_0|$ increases significantly for thicker blocking layers, which is consistent with our observation that the tips are much longer for

Figure 3.18: Summary of the results of COMSOL simulations for the radial component of the electric field. Comparison of the ramification threshold voltages from the experiments (red) and derived from the simulations (blue): (a) the layer thickness (L_i) and (b) the gap size (L) dependence. The reference radial electric field value in the simulation was calculated from the measurement with $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $L = 15 \mu\text{m}$ at a voltage of 53.4 V, therefore, for these values, the simulated and measured values coincide. The normalised radial electric field as a function of (c) the insulating layer thickness and (d) the gap size. Inset of (d) shows the contact angle dependence of the normalised radial electric field.

thicker insulating layers. The gap dependence of $|E_r/E_0|$ is illustrated in Figure 3.18d, where the value of $|E_r/E_0|$ decreases significantly for $L < 15 \mu\text{m}$, which explains the increase of U_R for cells with small gap size (Figure 3.15a).

The value of $|E_r/E_0|$ grew significantly when we decreased the contact angle at the triple junction, as the inset of Figure 3.18d shows. Considering this dependence can help to understand the localisation of branch growth near the substrate seen in Figure 3.11.

An interfacial instability similar to ramification was observed in sessile droplets of an FNLC placed on top of ferroelectric crystals [86]. In ref. [86], the phenomenon was explained by the interaction between the fringing electric field of the ferroelectric crystal and the bound charges created in topological defects of the spontaneous polarisation field in the FNLC.

Figure 3.19: The z component of the normalised electric field (E_z/E_0) as a function of the normalised radius (r/R_0), where R_0 is the base radius of the liquid bridge. E_z/E_0 was calculated in the middle of the liquid bridge at $z = 0$, marked by black dashed line in the left inset. (a) Radius dependence for different insulating layer thicknesses and (b) for different base radius values at $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$.

In general, the instability emerges, if a sufficiently large force acts against the surface tension, which tends to stabilise the liquid bridge. Assuming a 90° contact angle in the liquid bridge geometry, a radial electric force can be expressed as $F_e = E_r \cdot q$, where q represents an electric charge. The charge can have several origins. Although LC samples contain free charges, but their influence is usually neglected, especially in the presence of an AC electric field in the kHz range of frequency. To try the effect of ions, we doped a sample with a relatively high amount of an ionic salt (tetrabutyl ammonium benzoate (TBABE) in the weight concentration of 1% in RM734) during the measurements we found no significant change in the threshold voltage of the ramification instability.

Let us assume that the polarisation field has the same tangential structure as in sessile droplets. In presence of a radial electric field, a torque can act on the spontaneous polarisation, which tends to realign the polarisation field. Therefore, \mathbf{P} will have radial components that can induce surface charges at the LC-air interface: $\rho_s = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{u}$, where \mathbf{u} is the surface normal vector. The sign of ρ_s is different at the top and the bottom of the liquid bridge as E_r has also different signs according to Figure 3.17b, but the multiplication of the two will have the same sign. The electrostatic driving force of the ramification instability can be expressed by $p_e = E_r \cdot \rho_s$, which is a pressure-dimension quantity balanced by the stabilising effect of the surface tension at the threshold voltage.

Instabilities like the secondary, labyrinthine instability that we presented, have been observed in ferrofluids [57, 67–74] and in dielectrics [58] in presence of mag-

netic and electric fields, respectively. In both cases, the materials were investigated in between two flat bounding substrates with large lateral sizes compared to their distance (in Hele-Shaw cells). In those previous studies, plexiglass spacers were introduced between between the magnetic poles or the electrodes, which is an important similarity to our investigated geometries, where we applied insulating layers on the electrodes. According to the theoretical analysis discussed in [58] for dielectrics the driving force of the labyrinthine instability (F_L) is proportional with the inhomogeneity of the electric field ($F_L \sim (\varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_m)E_z \frac{dE_z}{dx}$), where ε_f is the permittivity of the investigated fluid and ε_m is the permittivity of the surrounding medium. The inhomogeneity of the field is due to the different voltage attenuation between the dielectrics with different permittivities.

In our simulations, we changed systematically the thickness of the insulating layer and the base radius of the liquid bridge (R_0). Figure 3.19 illustrates the normalised radius dependence of E_z/E_0 for several insulating layer thicknesses at $R_0 = 50 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 3.19a) and for several R_0 values at $L_i = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 3.19b). The value of E_z was measured at $z = 0$ along the black dashed line depicted in the inset of Figure 3.19a. For simplicity we assumed that the contact angle is 90° .

In Figure 3.19a, without insulating layer the $E_z/E_0 = 1$ in the whole sample. If $L_i \neq 0$, the vertical component of the field is larger closer to the LC-air interface and decreases to 1 close to the middle of the liquid bridge at $r/R_0 = 0$. If $L_i = 0$, the inhomogeneity of E_z disappears, which is consistent with the measurements as we could not observe the labyrinthine instability without blocking layer.

Figure 3.15b shows that the labyrinthine instability is strongly affected by the size, which is on one hand due to the increase in the effect of surface tension as the droplet size decreases [40]. On the other hand, the inhomogeneity of E_z also decreases for smaller droplets, as Figure 3.19b shows.

The required threshold voltage in [58] to induce the labyrinthine instability is in the range of 1-10 kV, but in our case it is an order of magnitude smaller. This is understandable as both F_L and $\frac{dE_z}{dx}$ are proportional with ε_f , which is in our case in the range of ~ 10000 [22], while $\varepsilon_f \approx 1 - 10$ for the used oils in ref. [58].

Figure 3.20: (a) The morphological phase diagram of ferroelectric liquid bridges as a function of voltage and frequency. The insets show the corresponding snapshots in the distinct regimes. Images of the active "febots" exhibiting translational motion with (b) horseshoe, (e) pear, (f) tuning-fork and (g) trident shape. The direction of motion is illustrated by red arrows. (c) Schematic illustration of the polarisation structures along the branches, which cause repulsion between the febots. (d) Time series snapshots of the motion and collision of two febots. Snapshots of rotating febots with (h) triskelion and (i) ring shape. Yellow bars correspond to $100 \mu\text{m}$.

3.2.3 Active matter state of ferroelectric nematics

The primary ramification and the secondary labyrinthine instabilities lead to a morphological shape change of the liquid bridges. We observed that depending on the magnitude and the frequency of the applied voltage signal, different regimes can be distinguished. In this section, we investigate the behaviour of RM734 in the liquid bridge geometry at high voltages depending on the applied fields' frequency and magnitude. The same sample parameters were used in all measurements, $L_i = 750 \text{ nm}$ and $L \approx 15 \mu\text{m}$, unless it is indicated differently.

Figure 3.20a displays the morphological phase diagram of ferroelectric nematic liquid bridges as a function of voltage and frequency. The insets of Figure 3.20a show the POM snapshots of droplets in the distinct regimes (taken with uncrossed

polarisers at 45°). Initially, upon application of AC sinusoidal voltage, the ramification instability leads to the formation of spiky structures on the contact lines above a threshold voltage. Increasing the voltage to a second threshold the labyrinthine instability occurs, causing deformation of the meniscus lines. During the secondary instability, the droplets lose their initially circular shape and, as a result, the quasi-rotational symmetry is disrupted. At higher voltages, two distinguishable behaviors of the droplets can be observed. At frequencies lower than 3 kHz, the meniscus lines continuously lengthen with increasing voltage, until the liquid bridges reach a critical surface to volume ratio, when they break up and reunite dynamically. Due to this 'dynamic breakup' the drops become a system of long interconnecting threads. At frequencies higher than 3 kHz, self-propelled motion of the deformed droplets can be observed above a threshold voltage. Depending on the initial size of the deformed liquid bridge, we observed different types of motion. The bigger drops form longer threads, which have chaotic motion. In case of smaller droplets or after the fragmentation of the bigger ones we could observe specific shapes exhibiting translational motion. Figure 3.20b-i present the most common shapes of the moving "hairy" objects, which we call "febots", where "fe" stands for ferroelectric and "bot" expresses that the units perform repetitive tasks such as bots or robots.

The typical shapes that exhibit translational motion are the horseshoe shape (Figure 3.20b) with two legs, the tuning-fork and trident shape with three legs (Figure 3.20f-g) and the pear shape with one leg (Figure 3.20e). We were also able to observe rotation motion of the febots in triskelton (Figure 3.20i) and ring shapes (Figure 3.20h). The translational movement direction of the febots is parallel to the symmetry axis of the febot's shape. Collision of febots often occurs during the movement, however, they do not merge, but avoid each other due to the repulsion between them. Figure 3.20d shows a series of snapshots about a collision between two febots. According to Figure 3.10a, the polarisation is parallel to the branches observable around the surface of the droplets; due to this structure, surface charges can accumulate that leads to repulsion between the febots. The polarisation structures are illustrated in Figure 3.20c.

For understanding the mechanism of the motion, we recorded videos with a fast camera, which we could use to capture the dynamics of the system within one period of the applied AC voltage. Figure 3.21 shows how a horseshoe-shaped febot changes its shape and optical properties in one period of the driving signal.

Figure 3.21: (a) The applied sinusoidal signal and the moments when the snapshots were made. Images of the febot in one period of the applied AC voltage: (b) in the non-active regime at 1 kHz and (c) in the active regime at 3 kHz. The numbers (1-4) represent the moments when the snapshots were taken.

We carried out the measurement at two frequencies: in the non-active regime at $f = 1$ kHz (Figure 3.21b) and in the active regime at $f = 3$ kHz (Figure 3.21c). At both frequencies, in each period the shape changes twice, independently of the field polarity. At close to 0 V, the darker appearance of the febot is observed due to the intense light scattering induced by the flipping of the polarisation, which induces strong electrohydrodynamic flow as the director dynamics and flow are coupled via the backflow effect [2]. The key distinction between the two frequencies is that at 1 kHz the shape of the meniscus line undergoes more noticeable changes than in the case of 3 kHz, which is understandable as the material has more time to relax back to the originally less deformed, more circular shape at 1 kHz. Although no net movement is visible within one period, analysing the long high-speed camera footage reveals that the movement is continuous, indicating that the elementary displacement takes place in one driving period, but it is too small to be observable.

We noticed that during the experiments, the samples produced sound while audio frequency voltage was applied in the N_F phase. Figure 3.22a shows the Fourier-transformed spectra of the emitted sound for different f frequencies marked by

Figure 3.22: (a) Spectra of the emitted sound for the driving frequencies in range 1-10 kHz at $U = 90$ V. The vertical axis shows the Fourier amplitudes (A_{FFT}) in arbitrary units on linear scale. The spectrum measured at 6 kHz is magnified separately. (b) Fourier amplitudes corresponding to the first and second harmonic signals as a function of the frequency. (c) The voltage dependence of the first and second harmonic Fourier amplitudes at $f = 6$ kHz. Inset shows the values corresponding to the first harmonic signal, magnified.

different colours at $U = 90$ V. The sound has components at the same frequency as the driving ($f_{\text{sound}} = f$, first harmonic), at double frequencies ($f_{\text{sound}} = 2f$, second harmonic) and at multiples of the second harmonic with smaller amplitudes. Figure 3.22b shows the Fourier amplitudes (A_{FFT}) of the first and second harmonic peaks as a function of the driving frequency; we marked the frequency regime, where the motion is observable. Figure 3.22c shows the voltage dependence of A_{FFT} at $f = 6$ kHz. The results indicate linear voltage dependence for the first harmonic signal as the inset of Figure 3.22c shows and higher order dependence for the second harmonic.

The observation of first harmonic signals refers to a linear electromechanical effect that is present only in the ferroelectric phase. The observed effect is a result of the absence of inversion symmetry, which gives rise to piezoelectricity. The strong second harmonic signals can be explained by electrostriction, due to the large effec-

Figure 3.23: Simulated trajectories corresponding to different types of motion: (a) Brownian motion, (b) non-chiral active Brownian motion and (c) chiral active Brownian motion with different handedness.

tive dielectric constant. We note that even a small amount of material, in the order of micrograms, can generate considerable sound in the ferroelectric nematic phase.

To analyse the properties of the motion, the trajectories of the febots were tracked by a custom-made tracking program (see Appendix A.5) implemented in Python using OpenCV [81]. Furthermore, we conducted statistical analysis using a model that describes active Brownian motion [87, 88]. In case of 2D active Brownian motion, the velocities are:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d}{dt}x(t) &= \sqrt{2D_T}\xi_x + v \cos \Psi(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt}y(t) &= \sqrt{2D_T}\xi_y + v \sin \Psi(t) \\ \frac{d}{dt}\Psi(t) &= \sqrt{2D_R}\xi_\Psi + \Omega\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

where $\mathbf{r} = (x, y)$ is the position vector of the active particle and Ψ is the orientation angle. ξ_x , ξ_y and ξ_Ψ are independent white noise stochastic processes with zero mean and no correlation. The fitting parameters of the model are the v average velocity, the D_T translational and D_R rotational diffusion coefficient. Ω describes the chirality of the system; if $\Omega = 0$ the system is achiral, if $\Omega \neq 0$ the particles tend to move on a spiral line. Figure 3.23 shows simulated trajectories with different parameter sets corresponding to different types of motion. Figure 3.23a shows the clearly Brownian motion trajectory ($v = 0, D_T \neq 0$), Figure 3.23b-c show the achiral active Brownian motion ($v \neq 0, D_T = 0, \Omega = 0$) and the chiral active Brownian motion with different handedness ($v \neq 0, D_T = 0, \Omega \neq 0$).

The febots were tracked at $f = 6$ kHz, in the voltage range where horseshoe-shaped febots were mostly observable. We recorded videos with a sample placed between circular polarisers with different handedness to increase the contrast of the febots. A snapshot from the recorded video at $U = 120$ V can be seen in Figure 3.24a. The inset of Figure 3.24a shows the structure of the tracked horseshoe shape.

Figure 3.24: (a) Snapshot of the sample used for tracking febots. The cell was placed between two circular polarisers with opposite handedness. The inset shows the structure of the tracked horseshoe shaped febot. (b) The tracked trajectories after the starting points were shifted to $(x, y) = (0, 0)$; each colour corresponds to a different febot. (c) The time averaged velocity distribution at $f = 6$ kHz and $U = 120$ V (d) The voltage dependence of the measured median velocity of horseshoe shaped febots at $f = 6$ kHz in a different cell. (e) Distribution of the mean orientation variations under 1 s.

Figure 3.24b shows the tracked trajectories after shifting their starting point to the origin. To analyse the velocity of febots, the trajectories were divided into parts corresponding to 1 second. The velocity was calculated for this 1 second time period with a moving average, $(\langle v \rangle_{\Delta t=1s} = \langle \frac{\Delta r}{\Delta t} \rangle_{\Delta t=1s})$. Figure 3.24c shows the distribution of $\langle v \rangle_{\Delta t=1s}$, from what we calculated the median velocity of the febots: $v_m \approx 300$ $\mu\text{m/s}$. Considering a single period of the driving voltage at $f = 6$ kHz, the mean displacement is around 50 nm, which clarifies why no translation was visible on the fast camera recordings in a single period. We also measured the voltage dependence of the median velocity in another sample as Figure 3.24d shows. The median velocity increases from 250 $\mu\text{m/s}$ to 450 $\mu\text{m/s}$, while the voltage increased from 100 V to 104 V.

Distribution of the time averaged orientation change in 1 s, $\langle \Delta\omega \rangle_{\Delta t=1s} = \langle \frac{\Delta\Psi}{2\Delta t} \rangle_{\Delta t=1s}$ is presented in Figure 3.24e. The distribution has a large peak at 0,

indicating mostly achiral ($\Omega = 0$) behaviour of the system. However, a secondary smaller peak can be observed at $\langle \Delta\omega \rangle_{\Delta t=1s} \sim -1.2$ rad/s that corresponds to left handed chiral motion.

By comparing the simulated and the tracked trajectories, we assumed that $D_T = 0$. To calculate the rotational diffusion coefficient, we made the following steps according to ref. [87]: (1) we split the trajectories into smaller parts ($\Delta t = 1$ s); (2) each part was translated and rotated to start at $\mathbf{r} = (0, 0)$ with orientation $\Psi = 0$; (3) the coordinates of the split trajectories were summarised and averaged. The average trajectory can be described by:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x(t) \rangle &= \frac{D_R}{v}(1 - e^{-D_R t}), \\ \langle y(t) \rangle &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where $\langle x(t) \rangle$ converges to $\Lambda_p = \frac{v}{D_R}$ for $t \rightarrow \infty$. Λ_p is the persistence length and it characterises the average distance before the orientation variation alters the direction of motion. As a result of fitting $\langle x(t) \rangle$, we obtained $D_R = 0.64 \frac{\text{rad}}{\text{s}}$ and $\Lambda_p = 434 \mu\text{m}$, which aligns with our observations on the long-time observability of febots in a 1 mm diameter region.

According to the COMSOL calculations, a large radial component of the electric field arises at the contact line in the liquid bridge geometry. Consequently, the Maxwell stress [89] is the strongest close to the contact line of the three materials (LC, air and blocking layer), which explains the observed movement towards the periphery and the strong second harmonic component in the emitted sound. Additionally, our acoustic experiments referred to that the FNLC exhibits piezoelectric properties, as it emits sounds at the first harmonic frequency. The strain induced by the piezoelectricity can also acts as a driving force of the displacement of the fluid at the perimeter. However, any driving forces acting perpendicular to the contact line average out in case of symmetrical objects. Indeed we found motility exclusively in febots with broken symmetry, and the direction of motion was always along a single mirror symmetry axis. Based on the working principle of inertial or stick-slip piezo actuators [90, 91], we propose that the main reason for the movement of febots is the local stick-slip motion of the contact line.

3.2.4 Summary and outlook

In Chapter 3.2 we presented two well distinguishable pattern forming instabilities of FNLC sessile droplets and liquid bridges in externally applied alternating electric fields. The requirement of both instabilities is the presence of relatively thick blocking layers on top of the electrodes.

The primary, ramification instability can be observed in all studied geometries above a threshold voltage. The instability occurs at the contact line located on the bounding substrates and results in branched, fractal-like structures. The frequency and the temperature dependences of the threshold voltage were investigated in normal and in-plane electric fields in different geometries, showing similar behaviors. The threshold voltage was found to have a minimum at $f \approx 1$ kHz. The instability can be observed even in the nematic phase close to T_{NNF} , but the threshold voltage increases significantly further from the ferroelectric phase. In case of surface electrodes, the branches emerge on top of the electrodes, where the electric field has mainly vertical component. By polarimetric microscopy measurements we proved that the polarisation aligns parallel to the branches, which can induce repulsion between neighbouring droplets. The well-developed instability leads to the formation of fractal structure in all studied geometries. The fractal dimension was determined in the wide electrode geometry with the value $\mathbb{H} = 1.61 \pm 0.1$.

In the liquid bridge geometry, by varying the thickness of the blocking layer we could control the length of the emerging branches, which proved that the layer thickness has a key role in the formation of the ramification instability. We also changed the cell gap systematically and we found that the threshold voltage increases for smaller gaps. We performed simulations to investigate the structure of the electric field in the liquid bridge geometry by using a simplified model of the FNLCs. We found that the presence of the blocking layer leads to the formation of significant radial electric field component close to the triple junction of the LC-air-blocking layer interfaces (at the contact line).

Similar instability to the ramification in FNLC droplets was observed on top of [86, 92], and in the vicinity of iron-doped lithium niobate ferroelectric crystals [93]. Additionally, in such a similar system, the direction of the emerging branches could be controlled by laser light [94].

The secondary instability is called labyrinthine instability, and it can be observed only in the liquid bridge geometry at higher voltages than the ramification. The labyrinthine instability induces the deformation of the liquid bridges' entire meniscus and forms a maze-like structure. The phenomenon shows analogy to Rosensweig's labyrinthine instability of ferrofluids [57, 67–74] and dielectrics [58]. However, in our system the required threshold voltage is significantly lower compared to the investigated dielectric fluids in ref. [58].

By varying the gap size of the cell, we found that the threshold voltage of the labyrinthine instability has a minimum at $\approx 15 - 20 \mu\text{m}$. We also showed that the threshold voltage increases significantly for small drop sizes.

In dielectrics, the driving force of the labyrinthine instability is the inhomogeneity of the vertical component of the electric field [58]. By simulations we showed that the requirement of the field's inhomogeneity is the presence of a blocking layer. We also investigated the drop size dependence and found that the inhomogeneity of the field decrease significantly for drops with smaller base radius.

Finally, we shed light on a new state of two-dimensional active matter consisting of droplets of ferroelectric nematics in a liquid bridge geometry. The electric field-induced surface instabilities in this geometry can lead to the fragmentation of droplets. By exploring the distinct morphologies of the droplets depending on the driving voltage and frequency, we revealed a special active state called "febots". The febots exhibit translational and rotational motion, displaying characteristic shapes such as horseshoe, tuning-fork, trident, pear, triskelion, and ring. Periodic shape changes of the febots were observed with double frequency of the driving signal by using high-speed camera recordings. We also detected and analysed the emission of sound during audio frequency voltage application in the ferroelectric phase. The spectra of the emitted sound with first harmonic component showing linear dependence on voltage indicate the existence of a linear electromechanical effect.

To analyse febot motion, we applied a model describing active Brownian motion. By tracking the trajectories of the febots, we determined important parameters of the febot motion, such as the average speed ($\approx 300 \mu\text{m/s}$) and the rotational diffusion coefficient ($\approx 0.64 \text{ rad/s}$). It was demonstrated that the velocity of the febots can be adjusted by altering the applied voltage.

3.3 Linear electromechanical effect in fluid ferroelectric nematics

During the measurements with ferroelectric nematics we observed that the samples emit sound, when we applied audio frequency AC voltages. In Chapter 3.2.3 we presented measurements, where we characterised the spectra of the emitted sound and identified components with the same frequency as the driving signal, indicating the presence of a linear electromechanical effect. However, the experimental arrangement did not allow a precise examination of the phenomenon. In this chapter, we describe converse piezoelectric measurements, which demonstrate piezoelectric effects observed in fluid FNLCs for the first time. During the investigations, the FNLC-919 room temperature liquid crystal was studied. The measurements were carried out at room temperature unless it is indicated differently. The gap between the ITO coated glass plates was set to 100 μm in the experimental setup described in Chapter 2.5.

In this study, we only measured the converse effect, which appeared as the periodic variation of the sample thickness induced by the applied AC voltage. We note that, the setup was designed to measure the direct piezoelectric response also when the sample is periodically deformed, and the electric response is measured. The amplitude and the phase of the time dependent acceleration were measured at the frequency of the driving signal (f) using the lock-in technique. At the base frequency, the amplitude of the periodic thickness change is given by $A_f = \Xi/(2\pi f)^2$, where Ξ is the acceleration. We also monitored the signal of the accelerometer by an oscilloscope to examine non-harmonic contributions.

As FNLCs are 3D fluids, they cannot sustain steady shear or compression in any direction. For electromechanical measurements, this means that the applied electric field must be alternating. This assumption is consistent with our measurements since no effect was observable when we applied DC voltages.

Figure 3.25a-b shows the time dependence of the acceleration (red) and the applied voltage (blue) for $U = 2$ V and $U = 5$ V respectively at $f = 3$ kHz. At $U = 2$ V, the mechanical response of the sample is purely linear but at higher voltage a second harmonic contribution to the signal, attributed to electrostriction is also observed. To our knowledge, the first harmonic response is only possible via the converse piezoelectric effect predicted in Eq. (1.12). We measured the amplitude of

Figure 3.25: Time dependences of the applied voltage (blue lines, plotted against the right axes) and of the acceleration of the cover plate (red line, plotted against the left axes) of a $100 \mu\text{m}$ thick FNLc 919 sample at $f = 3$ kHz, (a) $U = 2$ V and (b) $U = 5$ V. Amplitude of vertical vibrations of the top plate (A_f) at the frequency of the applied field under various conditions: (c) frequency dependence of A_f at $U = 5$ V, (d) voltage dependence of A_f at $f = 3$ kHz. The inset shows the temperature dependence of A_f at $U = 2$ V, $f = 3$ kHz sinusoidal voltage.

the vibration (A_f) as a function of the frequency at $U = 5$ V as Figure 3.25c shows. The graph has several peaks that indicate resonance effects at different frequencies related to the geometry and the mechanical properties of the measuring system. We observed higher values (~ 100 nm) of A_f at the low frequency region and smaller values (~ 10 nm) at the higher frequency region above 1 kHz.

In the current geometry, the strain (ζ) is the ratio of the amplitude of vibration (A_f) to the film thickness (L), $\zeta = A_f/L$. The applied electric field is $E \sim U/L$, which gives the measured piezoelectric coupling constant as $\gamma = A_f/U$. To determine γ , we measured A_f as a function of the applied voltage and fitted the data by a linear function at different frequencies. The voltage dependence of A_f and the fitting is illustrated in Figure 3.25d at $f = 3$ kHz. The value of γ for the low frequency region was in range $\gamma(f < 1 \text{ kHz}) \sim 6 \cdot 10^{-8}$ m/V and for $f > 1$ kHz $\gamma(f > 1 \text{ kHz}) \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m/V. These values yield strong linear electromechanical effect as they are comparable with the highest values found so far in crystals [93, 95].

The linear electromechanical response decreases as we increase the temperature, illustrated in the inset of Figure 3.25d. Above the transition to the nematic phase the value of A_f becomes essentially immeasurable, which demonstrates that the linear electromechanical effect is a unique property of the N_F phase.

To comprehend the context of the measurement with the phenomenon as described in chapter 1.6.2 and to assume the maximum achievable converse piezoelectric performance in this new class of materials, it is useful to compare the ideal geometries to the actual construction assembled in the laboratory. As we did not use any alignment layers during the measurement, the compound was in direct contact with the ITO layers. The surface alignment of the ITO layer provides random planar orientation that induced the appearance of Schlieren texture [30], which was verified in an independent measurement using sandwich cells. Figure 1.14 illustrates that in planar alignment, zero converse piezoelectricity is expected due to the tensor element $\gamma_{x,xx}$, which is zero by symmetry. Piezoelectricity detectable by our experimental geometry can emerge when there is a component of polarisation along the field, specifically when $\gamma_{z,zz}$ becomes effective.

In practice, ideal planar alignment, where the director lies precisely in the plane of the bounding surface, cannot be achieved. The planar alignment always exhibit a small 'pre-tilt' angle (Θ), between the director (and thus the direction of polarisation) and the electrode plane, which results in a vertical component of the polarisation: $\approx P_s \sin \Theta$. In addition, due to the random planar surface orientation, defects can accumulate close to the bounding plates that can also lead to the bending of the director out of the x - y plane, which also increase the average vertical component of \mathbf{P}_s .

In reference [P3], besides FNLC-919, an additional ferroelectric nematic (FNLC-1571) was investigated by using an another measuring system. For FNLC-1571, the approximated minimum value of the pretilt was calculated. The result predicted a pretilt for parallel rubbed planar cell $\Theta < 1^\circ$, which indicates that by considering a possibly higher value of Θ , the estimated maximum value of γ can be even larger. In our geometry, the value of Θ is assumed to be larger due the presence of the Schlieren texture and the measured value of γ was an order of magnitude larger than for FNLC-1571 in a planar cell.

The obvious step would be to use homeotropic surface alignment to measure the maximum value of γ . However, the geometry where the polarisation is perpendicular

to the bounding surfaces is particularly difficult to achieve since there a depolarising electric field is induced, which inhibits the desired alignment. In principle, achieving homeotropic alignment or increasing the pre-tilt angle potentially allows for a dramatic (perhaps ten or hundred times) augmentation of the electromechanical effects we report here.

3.3.1 Summary and outlook

In Chapter 3.3, linear electromechanical effects corresponding to converse piezoelectricity have been observed and analysed in room temperature fluid ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals. The derived piezoelectric coupling constant was found to be comparable to or exceeding that of the strongest solid piezoelectric materials. Our assumptions indicate much larger γ values reachable by increasing the pretilt of the samples.

Future research directions will concentrate on to achieve higher piezoelectric signals and to explore the direct piezoelectric effects in FNLCS. Our primary observations are significant, since linear electromechanical coupling is an inherent property of ferroelectric materials, but so far has only been explored in crystals, polymers, and positionally ordered liquid crystals.

3.4 Fluid ferroelectric filaments

During the preparation of sessile droplets or while working with room temperature FNLCs, we noticed that all compounds tend to form long filaments with lengths in the range of centimetres. In this chapter, first, we present the filament formation ability of a FNLC. Later, we show the behaviour of the filaments, when we applied DC and AC voltages with different wave shapes (sinusoidal, square, and triangular wave). Finally, we present a theoretical description of the filament formation of the FNLCs and we determine some physical quantities of the used compound. In the measurements, we used the FNLC-919 room temperature ferroelectric liquid crystal produced by Merck. All measurements were conducted at room temperature unless it is indicated differently.

During our work with the room temperature FNLC, we observed when attempting to remove it from a vial, it forms filaments that can be drawn several centimetres before rupturing. To characterise the effect, we placed a sessile drop on a glass plate and touched it with a glass rod, which was attached to a vertical micropositioner. As shown in Figure 3.26b1, when the rod is pulled out of the compound, it initially forms an hourglass shape with a narrow waist that is approximately $100\ \mu\text{m}$ thick. When we pulled the rod further a filament with uniform thickness was formed, as seen in Figure 3.26b2-b4. The diameter of the filament (d) was in the range of $10\ \mu\text{m}$. We measured the filament's thickness while we pulled it. By assuming cylindrical symmetry, we were able to calculate its volume as a function of length L . The results are shown in the main pane of Figure 3.26a. After an initial linear increase, the volume stabilised, indicating that the material flow from the bottom reservoir has stopped and the length was increased at the cost of thickness. The maximum length can easily be over two orders of magnitude larger than of its diameter (aspect ratio, $a = \frac{L}{d} > 100$) before it bursts. The captured video of the pulling process can be seen in Supplemental Video 1 of [P4].

Figure 3.26c1-c3 shows POM snapshots of the filament during the pulling process. The filament appears bright, when the transmitting axis of the polarisers is at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the filament (Figure 3.26c2) and it appears dark when the polariser (analyser) is parallel (perpendicular) to it (Figure 3.26c3), which indicates that the optical axis of the material and so the polarisation is parallel or perpendicular to the filament according to Eq. 2.1.

Figure 3.26: Summary of the behaviour of FNLC filaments without externally applied electric fields. (a) Length dependence of the volume of an FNLC-919 filament. Insets (b1-b4) show the vertically aligned thread at different lengths. Yellow bars correspond to $100\ \mu\text{m}$. Snapshots of a filament (c1) without polarisers, (c2) between crossed polarisers at nearly $\pm 45^\circ$ and (c3) at 0° and 90° with respect to the horizontal direction. (d) Time dependence of the electric current induced by the pulling process (blue line plotted against the left axis) and the area of the waist of the thread (red line plotted against the right axis). (e) Side views of the bridges at selected times shown by green arrows. d denotes the diameter of the filament.

The longest and most stable filaments are typically pulled first from a sessile droplet. However, their ability to form fibres gradually disappears after about an hour of exposure to air. Additionally, higher humidity levels result in shorter lifetimes and reduced fibre formation ability. Stable filaments also become unstable and rupture if the two sides are short-circuited. It is not possible to pull a long and stable filament if its ends are connected by a conductor or grounded. The observations suggest that the formation and destabilisation of the filament have electrostatic origin.

By using an ITO coated glass as the base plate for the sessile droplet and a metal wire for pulling a fibre, we were able to measure the electric current flowing through the material during the pulling process (refer to the blue line in Figure 3.26d). Simultaneously, we measured the diameter of the liquid bridge (d) as a function of time and calculated its area (see the red line plotted against the right axis in Figure 3.26d) as $\mathcal{A} = (\frac{d}{2})^2\pi$. Figure 3.26e displays various side views of the FNLC bridge at different stages of the pulling process. The corresponding snapshots for Figure 3.26d

are marked by green arrows. During the first half of the pulling, no current flowed through the bridge. A sharp current peak arose when the thin filament formed, indicating realignment of the ferroelectric polarisation. We note that the direction of the peak was found to be arbitrary, and practically no current was observed in the N phase throughout the entire meniscus range before the bridge collapsed.

If the compound was between conducting surfaces and sufficiently large DC voltage was applied, it could stabilise the filaments and we were able to pull threads even from those materials that have been exposed to air for a long time. The filaments remained stable as long as the voltage was applied and they collapsed immediately, when it was switched off. To analyse the stabilising ability of the applied voltage, we measured the maximum length, when the threads ruptured (L_{max}) as a function of DC voltage, shown in Figure 3.27a. In the measurement, we placed the FNLC between two wires with diameter $80\ \mu\text{m}$. The wires were attached to micropositioners, so we could change the distance between them precisely. At a given voltage value, the wires started to be separated from each other until the fibre broke. The applied voltage started to stabilize the filament above $U = 3\ \text{V}$. Below this voltage, the thread became unstable at the aspect ratio $a \sim 1.5$, which is close to the Plateau-Rayleigh limit of $a = \pi$. Above $U = 3\ \text{V}$, L_{max} increased proportional to the applied voltage. Snapshots of the DC voltage stabilised filaments ($U = 20\ \text{V}$) are shown in Figure 3.27b-e and in the Supplemental Video 2 of [P4]. It can be seen that the filament is straight and shows no sagging, in contrast to the high voltage (20 kV) stabilized water bridges, presented in Chapter 1.5. The aspect ratio before breaking can reach over 100 and the thread is completely stable up to $a = 50$.

Figures 3.27f-g show transmission images of a DC stabilised filament doped with a dichroic dye (disperse orange 3 from Sigma-Aldrich) and illuminated by blue light polarised horizontally (Figure 3.27f) and vertically (Figure 3.27g). The dichroic dye consists of rod-like molecules that are aligned parallel to the director and it exhibits higher light absorption along the polarisation of light (Figure 3.27f) and higher transmittance for the perpendicular case (Figure 3.27g). Consequently, Figures 3.27f-g prove that the director and so the electric polarisation is parallel to the long axis of the filament. The alignment of the dye molecules along the director was confirmed by an experiment using a parallel rubbed planar sandwich cell.

The filaments can also be stabilised and pulled in the presence of low frequency AC voltages. However, in this case, compared to the static shapes with DC volt-

Figure 3.27: Summary of the observations on FNLC filaments in longitudinal DC fields. (a) Maximum length L_{max} as a function of DC voltage applied between two supporting wires ($80 \mu\text{m}$ diameter). Insets (b)-(e) show the filament at increasing length and slenderness ratio a =length/diameter, while pulling in presence of $U = 20 \text{ V}$ DC voltage. (f) and (g) show observation in transmission of a piece of horizontal thread doped with a dichroic dye (disperse orange 3) and illuminated by blue light polarised (f) horizontally and (g) vertically.

ages, they show dynamic behaviour. At frequencies lower than 50 Hz we observed transversal vibrations of the filaments driven by the axial electric field. Fast camera snapshots of the vibration between wires with diameter $d = 200 \mu\text{m}$ can be seen in Figure 3.28b at $f = 40 \text{ Hz}$, $U = 50 \text{ V}$ sinusoidal voltage. The oscillation was symmetric about a slightly downward sagged position. This is related to gravity that pulls the thread downward. The amplitude of the vibration (at a fixed f and U) can be adjusted by varying the length (refer to Figure 3.28d).

The vibration can be also tuned by changing the frequency at a given length. The amplitude of the vibration A_0 at constant length ($L = 2.5 \text{ mm}$) as a function of frequency under 70 V sinusoidal voltage is shown in Figure 3.28b. Amplitude of the vibration was determined by using a custom-made evaluation program based on image processing (see Appendix (A.6)). $A_0(f)$ exhibits multiple minima and maxima below 50 Hz , which increases with frequency, indicating a coupled driven oscillation with a natural frequency above 50 Hz .

The vibration dynamics exhibit different behaviour when a square wave signal is applied, as opposed to a sinusoidal wave. By switching the polarity of a 50 V DC voltage, a transversal vibration was generated that faded away with time. Figure 3.28a shows the displacement of a filament (x) as a function of time after the polarity change. The thread was $L = 3 \text{ mm}$ long with $d = 200 \mu\text{m}$ diameter. $x(t)$ can be described by damped oscillation that can be fitted by an exponentially decaying

Figure 3.28: Summary of the transversal vibration of FNLC filaments in longitudinal non-steady electric fields. (a) The transversal displacement as a function of time ($x(t)$) of a 3 mm long oscillating thread after the sign inversion of 50 V DC voltage. (b) Snapshots of a filament at different phases during the oscillation, while we applied $U = 50$ V, $f = 40$ Hz sinusoidal signal. (c) Frequency dependence of the A_0 oscillation amplitude for 70 V sinusoidal voltage applied horizontally. (d) Standing waves on a thread with different length when we applied $U = 90$ V, $f = 20$ Hz sinusoidal signal.

cosine function, $x(t) = A_0 \exp(-\Gamma t) \cos(\omega_1 t - \varphi_0) + x_0$, where A_0 is the amplitude, Γ is the damping coefficient, ω_1 and φ_0 are the angular frequency of the damped oscillator and the phase and x_0 is a fitting offset. By fitting the data we get $\omega_1 \approx 480$ s^{-1} and $\Gamma \approx 32.5$ s^{-1} , which corresponds to a weak damping ($\Gamma \ll \omega_1$), where the natural angular frequency of the undamped oscillator is very close to that of the damped one, and to the resonance angular frequency (ω_0) in the driven case ($\omega_1 \approx \omega_0$) [89]. In elastic strings with Young's modulus Y , $\omega_0 = \frac{\pi}{L} \sqrt{\frac{Y}{\rho}}$. By using the density $\rho \approx 1.3 \cdot 10^3$ kg/m^3 measured for room temperature ferroelectric nematics [96], we get $Y = 273$ Pa. The damping coefficient (Γ) can be related to the flow viscosity of the material as $\Gamma \approx \frac{\eta \pi^2}{2\rho L^2}$, for simplicity we neglect the damping from air [97]. From the parameters described above, this provides $\eta \approx 77$ mPas viscosity, which is typical for room temperature ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals [98].

We measured the time dependence of the electric current flowing through the thread during applied triangular AC voltages between $d = 400$ μm wires. Simultaneously, we recorded a video of the filament between parallel and crossed polarisers at 45° with respect to the filament. Figure 3.29a shows the time dependence of the electric current flowing in an $L = 500$ μm long thread under 40 V, 20 Hz triangular wave voltage. Close to the polarity change of the voltage, a current peak can be observed induced by the reversal of the spontaneous polarisation.

Figure 3.29: (a) Time dependence of the electric current flowing (blue line plotted against the left axis) in a $500 \mu\text{m}$ long $400 \mu\text{m}$ diameter thread under 40 V , 20 Hz triangular wave voltage (red line plotted against the right axis). (b) Voltage dependence of the electric charge accumulated on the wires, calculated from the area below the polarisation peak observable in (a). Inset shows the time dependence of the electric current under sign inversion of 40 V , 10 Hz square wave voltage. (c)-(d) Snapshots taken at different times corresponding to (a), with parallel (upper row) and crossed polarisers (lower row).

The sign of the peak depends on the direction of the polarity change. Figure 3.29c and Figure 3.29e show the snapshots of the filament when the absolute value of the driving voltage was close to the maximum. The high intensity transmitted through the fibre between crossed polarisers indicates that the director and thus the polarisation was parallel to the axis of the thread, similarly to the DC measurements (Figure 3.27). It can be observed that the shape of the filament was not the same for opposite polarities. This deviation is probably caused by the axial flows occurring in the fibre leading to push-pull effect; similar phenomena were observed in bent-core ferroelectric smectic materials [99]. Such an effect may be related to the linear electromechanical behaviour of the FNLCS discussed in Chapter 3.3. At the polarity reversal, the intensity of the transmitted light decreased due to the strong light scattering induced by chaotic flow, as illustrated in Figure 3.29d.

Figure 3.29b displays the voltage dependence of the electric charge, calculated by the area below the electric current peak in Figure 3.29a. Based on the saturated value

of $Q_s \approx 7$ nC and the area of the wire's cross-section ($d = 400$ μm), we can estimate the spontaneous polarisation of the FNLC-919 compound: $|\mathbf{P}_s| = Q_s / (2(\frac{d}{2})^2\pi) \approx 3$ $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. This value is similar to those measured on other FNLC materials [19, 23, 100]. We note that no polarisation peak was observed in the N phase.

The time dependence of the electric current after sign inversion of a 40 V, 10 Hz square wave voltage is shown in the inset of Figure 3.29b. The peak position of the current suggests a switching time of $\tau \approx 1$ ms, which is typical for FNLC materials.

A possible way of the fluid filament formation is the presence of an elastic term in addition to the surface tension to overcome the Plateau-Rayleigh instability. Good examples are the smectic and columnar liquid crystal fibres, where the bulk elastic term is provided by the layer and column compression modulus, respectively [1]. A thread made of a viscoelastic material, which can be modelled by a spring and a dashpot connected in series, will relax over time with a relaxation time of $\tau = \eta/Y$ [101]. Therefore, at a constant temperature, the thread should collapse consistently at the same time after it is formed. For our system, this gives $\tau \approx 280$ μs , but in the experiments the filaments without external electric field remained stable approximately an order longer. We observed that the lifetime of the fibres largely depends on how long they were exposed to air, to humidity or whether their ends were short-circuited or not. This suggests they can be destabilised by free electric charges (ionic contaminations). Likewise, this also suggests that the stabilisation of ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal filaments is due to an electrostatic interaction.

We observed that the external DC electric field can stabilise the FNLC filaments (Figure 3.27). We will show that a DC electric field is also formed in the case of free-standing thread, induced by bound charges. In case of the experiments without external electric field, we saw that the polarisation field was realigned during the pulling process (Figure 3.26b). We note that our conclusion of that the polarisation lies along the fibre (see Figure 3.27f-g) was confirmed by a second harmonic generation measurement [98]. Figure 3.30 shows the schematic drawing of the free standing filament formation process, when the material is on insulating surfaces. In the initial state, there are two separated sessile droplets, shown in Figure 3.30a. Knowing that the polarisation field in sessile droplets has tangential structure with a defect core in the middle, we illustrated the estimated \mathbf{P}_s field in Figure 3.30a by red arrows. By bringing the base plates closer, a liquid bridge forms from the sessile droplets with the same tangential structure of \mathbf{P}_s (Figure 3.30b). If we increase the distance

Figure 3.30: (a-c) Illustration of the physical mechanism leading to FNLC filaments. (a) Sessile droplets with tangential polarisation field before touching each other. (b) Fluid bridge with hour-glass shape and polarisation along the substrates. (c) Formation of the filament with parallel polarisation and bound charges at the ends. (d) Illustration of the forces acting on the liquid bridge in external electric field, where F_{elec} can be calculated from the Maxwell stress, F_{surf} is the force of the surface tension and g , m are the gravitational acceleration and the mass of the thread.

between the plates, the necking occurs and the filament forms between the two sessile droplets, shown in Figure 3.30c. The sessile droplets have the same tangential director field configuration containing only bend (no splay) deformation, whereas in the filament, the director is aligned along the thread. As a consequence, at the part, where the filament connects to the sessile droplet, splay deformation of the polarisation field has to develop. Therefore, the two cones have a charge density $\rho_b = -\nabla P_s$. As the splay direction is opposite in the two cones, while the polarisation direction is the same, the charge densities have opposite signs. This results in an attractive force between the two ends of the filament that can balance the pulling force, thus stabilising the filament.

The magnitude of the bound charge density decreases to zero gradually from the cone with pure splay toward the bulk of the sessile droplet with pure bend (no splay). Assuming that the length of the splay deformation is comparable with the radius of the filament (R), the maximum value of the potential difference U between the bound charges can be estimated from the Coulombic polarisation splay force F_C as:

$$U \approx EL = \frac{F_C}{Q}L = k\frac{Q}{L} \sim k\frac{\nabla P \cdot V}{L} \sim k\frac{PR^2}{L} \quad (3.5)$$

where $k \approx 9 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Nm}^2/\text{C}^2$ is the Coulomb constant and V is the volume of the cone with splay deformation. For the measurement presented in Figure 3.26a, with $L = 1 \text{ cm}$ and $R = 36 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ this formula gives $U \approx 33 \text{ V}$, which is larger than

the smallest voltage that stabilized an $R = 80 \mu\text{m}$ thread shown in Figure 3.27a. For a similarly thick filament, the potential difference between the bound charges would be even larger, $U \sim 270 \text{ V}$. Although that voltage is likely decreased due to the screening effect originating from free charges, we can safely conclude that the explanation of the freestanding filaments without externally applied voltage is similar to the explanation for the stability of the stable threads due to externally applied axial voltage. The difference between filaments with and without external fields is that the former experience a potential difference due to the bound charges, while the latter are stabilised by externally applied voltage.

The driving force behind the stabilisation is the reduction of free energy when the material is in electric field. The free energy density f of a ferroelectric material in electric field is given by (see Chapter 1.4.2):

$$f = f_0 + f_E = f_0 - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_0\hat{\varepsilon}\mathbf{E}^2 - \mathbf{P}_s\mathbf{E}. \quad (3.6)$$

For any positive dielectric constant and when $\mathbf{P}_s\mathbf{E} > 0$, the electric field can reduce the free energy, thus forces the liquid to be inside an electric field. The ratio of the ferroelectric and dielectric terms for a typical electric field value $E \sim 2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ V/m}$ is $\frac{2P}{\varepsilon_0\varepsilon E} \sim 30$ even if the dielectric constant is as large as $\varepsilon \sim 10^4$. Therefore, the ferroelectric term is dominant, and the dielectric term can be neglected. In this approximation, the magnitude of the force that pulls the fluid along the thread with radius R in cylindrical coordinate system is:

$$F_{elec} = - \iiint_{0,0,0}^{L,2\pi,R} \nabla f_E r dr d\varphi dz \approx \iiint_{0,0,0}^{L,2\pi,R} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} E r dr d\varphi dz \sim R^2 \pi P E. \quad (3.7)$$

And the force due to the surface tension (Υ) in the range where the filament thickness is constant:

$$F_{surf} = -\frac{\partial(\Upsilon\mathcal{S})}{\partial L} = -\frac{\partial(\Upsilon 2\pi RL)}{\partial L} = -2\pi\Upsilon R, \quad (3.8)$$

where \mathcal{S} is the surface of the thread. The balance between the two forces gives an opportunity to estimate the maximum fibre length (L_{max}) as a function of the applied voltage: $L_{max} = \frac{RP}{2\Upsilon}U$. The model predicts linear voltage dependence that we also observed above $U = 15 \text{ V}$ in the measurement presented in Figure 3.27a, where the diameter of the filament remained constant. The fitted slope ($L_{max}/U \approx 6 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m/V}$) can be used to calculate the surface tension as $\Upsilon \approx \frac{RP}{2(L_{max}/U)} \approx 3 \cdot 10^{-3}$

N/m. This value is plausible, considering the reducing effect of the spontaneous polarisation on the surface tension in ferroelectric nematics [86].

In case of DC voltage stabilised water bridges, a sagging of the filament can be observed, while in our case the filament seems completely straight. The equilibrium shape of the thread can be determined from the balance of the forces acting on the filament, illustrated in Figure 3.30d. The force of gravity pulls the filament down, $F_g = mg$, while the stabilising force is $2(F_{elec} + F_{surf}) \cdot \sin \beta$, where β is the angle between the horizontal and the cable tangent at the support (see Figure 3.30d). The main contribution to the tension is electrical, so we can neglect the surface term. This has been demonstrated even in cases of water with higher surface tension, lower permittivity, and no spontaneous polarisation [43, 47]. If we also neglect the dielectric part of F_{elec} , this leads to the relation $h = \frac{L(\sec \beta - 1)}{\ln((1 + \sin \beta)/(1 - \sin \beta))}$ between the depth of sagging and β , and $\sin \beta = \frac{\rho g L_s}{PE}$ between β and the applied electric field, where ρ is the density and $L_s = \frac{2L \tan \beta}{\ln((1 + \sin \beta)/(1 - \sin \beta))}$ is the sagged length of the thread measured along the tangent line [47]. By combining the relations β can be estimated as $\sin \beta \approx 0.03$, indicating negligible sagging in agreement with our experiments.

3.4.1 Summary and outlook

In Chapter 3.4 we described slender fluid filaments of a room-temperature ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal. The filaments can be stabilised by either internal electric fields of bound charges formed due to polarisation splay or by external voltage applied between the suspending wires. The slenderness ratio can exceed 100, however, without external electric fields, the fluid ferroelectric filament becomes unstable over time due to ionic screening of the bound charges.

The origin of the electric stabilisation in ferroelectric nematic materials is comparable to that observed in dielectric fluids like water [41]. However, the voltages required for stabilisation are three orders of magnitude smaller in ferroelectric nematic materials. Furthermore, low-frequency AC voltages can be used also for stabilisation, which result in transversal damped vibrations. The ferroelectric tension and viscosity of the material were determined through the fitting of these vibrations.

The shape and the length of the filaments are determined by the balance between electrostatic and interfacial forces in the static case. In the dynamic case, the material flow and viscous forces also play role.

Our results also provide a new technique for reproducible measurements of the ferroelectric polarisation. In addition to their scientific interest, ferroelectric nematic materials may have practical applications. One possibility is their use in nanofluidic devices, as suggested for water channels [102]. Ferroelectric nematic materials have advantages over water, including the three orders of magnitude lower voltage requirement and the non-volatility. Axial field-induced bridging can be used in various applications such as micron-sized logic devices, switches, and relays.

Similar effects and non-linear optical behaviour of standing and electrically suspended ferroelectric fluid bridges were also investigated by Alexander et al. [98], which also indicates the relevance of the actual topic.

Appendix A: Appendix: Evaluation programs

During the experiments, the raw measurement data were in most cases videos or images. To evaluate the recorded images, I used custom-made evaluation programs implemented in Python. In this chapter, I discuss the main steps of the used evaluation programs that I developed.

A.1 Angular velocity of the tracers in thermomotor effect

To determine the angular velocity of the tracers in sessile droplets, first, I recorded images in equal time intervals ($\Delta t = 1$ s) in transmission mode without polarisers. The main steps of the evaluation program are the following:

1. conversion of the images into grayscale,
2. averaging the grayscale images to calculate a background image,
3. subtracting the background image from all images to increase the contrast of the tracer particles,
4. calculation of the rotation angle of the tracers between neighbouring images by rotating the images and subtracting them while calculating the average intensity of the difference. The rotation angle is where the average intensity has a minimum,
5. the angular velocity can be calculated from the rotation angle and the Δt time difference between the neighbouring images.

A.2 Threshold voltage calculation of the ramification instability in the in-plane electrode geometry

To determine the threshold voltage of the ramification instability in the in-plane electrode geometry, first, I recorded images of the sessile droplet while the applied voltage was changed systematically. The main steps of the evaluation program are the following:

1. conversion of the images into grayscale,
2. calculation of the 2D Fourier transform of the images,
3. filtering out the strong peaks in the Fourier transformed image corresponding to the periodic electrode structure,
4. inverse Fourier transformation of the images,
5. converting the images into a binary image with a predefined threshold value,
6. finding the contour of the droplet with the OpenCV contour finding method and calculation of the length of the contour, which is the perimeter of the droplet,
7. plotting the perimeter as function of the applied voltage and fitting the data with the $\mathcal{F}(U)$ function according to Eq. (3.1).

A.3 Threshold voltage calculation of the ramification instability in the liquid bridge geometry

To determine the threshold voltage of the ramification instability in the liquid bridge geometry, first, I recorded images of the liquid bridge while the applied voltage was changed systematically. The main steps of the evaluation program are the following:

1. conversion of the images into grayscale,

2. conversion of the image corresponding to $U = 0$ V to a binary image with a predefined threshold value to find the meniscus line (the meniscus line is black in the images),
3. finding the contour of the meniscus line with the contour finding method of OpenCV
4. fitting the meniscus line with an ellipse,
5. transformation and re-plotting the vicinity of the meniscus line in a new coordinate system by using the fitted ellipse,
6. calculation of the roughness of the surface according to Eq. (3.2),
7. plotting the roughness of the surface as a function of the applied voltage and fitting the data with $\mathcal{F}(U)$ function according to Eq. (3.1).

A.4 Calculation of the length of the meniscus line

To calculate the length of the meniscus line in the liquid bridge geometry, first, I recorded images of the liquid bridge in transmission mode without polarisers. The main steps of the evaluation program are the following:

1. conversion of the images into grayscale,
2. conversion of the images into binary images by using a predefined threshold value (the meniscus line is black in the images),
3. finding the contour of the meniscus line by using the contour finding method of OpenCV,
4. calculating the length of the contour.

A.5 Trajectory tracking of the febots

To track the motion of the febots, first, I recorded a video of the motion with constant frame rate (50 fps) between circular polarisers with opposite handedness. The main steps of the tracking program are the following:

1. calculation of the approximate location of the febots in every frame by searching for local maxima points,
2. calculating the centres of the febots by calculating the coordinate averages weighted by the pixel intensities in the vicinities of the local maxima points,
3. at the first frame: adding a new label to each found febot,
4. calculating the Euclidean distance between the febots in the neighbouring frames, if the distance is smaller than a predefined threshold value identifying the febot with the same label on the neighbouring frames.

A.6 Finding the centre line of liquid fibres

To find the centre line of the liquid threads and to calculate the amplitude of the vibration, first, I recorded a video without polarisers with constant frame rates (~ 1000 fps). The main steps of the evaluation program are the following:

1. conversion of the frames into grayscale,
2. conversion into binary image by using a predefined threshold value,
3. rotating the images until the long axis of the threads became horizontal,
4. using Laplacian filter to increase the contrast of the edge of the threads,
5. plotting the vertical pixels and finding the edge of the threads by using peak finding method,
6. calculating the centre of the thread by averaging the coordinates of the edges.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Jakli and A. Saupe. *One- and two-dimensional fluids*. Taylor & Francis, New York, 2009. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13583140902940347>.
- [2] P. De Gennes and J. Prost. *The physics of liquid crystals*. Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1993.
- [3] C. Kittel. *Introduction to solid state physics*. John Wiley & sons, inc, 2005. ISBN: 0-471-68057-5.
- [4] G. Busch. “Early history of ferroelectricity”. In: *Ferroelectrics* 74.1 (1987), pp. 267–284. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00150198708201307>.
- [5] J. Valasek. “Piezo-electric and allied phenomena in Rochelle salt”. In: *Physical Review* 17.4 (1921), 475 – 481. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.17.475>.
- [6] J. F. Scott. “Applications of Modern Ferroelectrics”. In: *Science* 315.5814 (2007), pp. 954–959. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1129564>.
- [7] R.E. Rosensweig. *Ferrohydrodynamics*. Dover Books on Physics. Dover Publications, New York, 2013. ISBN: 9780486783000.
- [8] A. Mertelj, N. Osterman, D. Lisjak, and M. Čopič. “Magneto-optic and converse magnetoelectric effects in a ferromagnetic liquid crystal”. In: *Soft Matter* 10.45 (2014), 9065 – 9072. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4sm01625d>.
- [9] C.P. Bean and J.D. Livingston. “Superparamagnetism”. In: *Journal of Applied Physics* 30.4 (1959), S120 – S129. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2185850>.
- [10] C. Scherer and A.M. Figueiredo Neto. “Ferrofluids: Properties and applications”. In: *Brazilian Journal of Physics* 35.3 A (2005), 718 – 727. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-97332005000400018>.
- [11] I. Torres-Díaz and C. Rinaldi. “Recent progress in ferrofluids research: Novel applications of magnetically controllable and tunable fluids”. In: *Soft Matter* 10.43 (2014), 8584 – 8602. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4sm01308e>.

- [12] M. Born. “Zur Raumgittertheorie des Diamanten”. In: *Annalen der Physik* 349.12 (1914), 605 – 642. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19143491209>.
- [13] S. T. Lagerwall. “Ferroelectric and Antiferroelectric Liquid Crystals”. In: *Ferroelectrics* 301.1 (2004), pp. 15–45. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00150190490464827>.
- [14] S. Furukawa, J. Wu, M. Koyama, K. Hayashi, N. Hoshino, T. Takeda, Y. Suzuki, J. Kawamata, M. Saito, and T. Akutagawa. “Ferroelectric columnar assemblies from the bowl-to-bowl inversion of aromatic cores”. In: *Nature Communications* 12.1 (2021). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21019-4>.
- [15] N. A. Clark and S. T. Lagerwall. “Submicrosecond bistable electro-optic switching in liquid crystals”. In: *Applied Physics Letters* 36.11 (2008), pp. 899–901. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.91359>.
- [16] M. A. Handschy and N. A. Clark. “Structures and responses of ferroelectric liquid crystals in the surface-stabilized geometry”. In: *Ferroelectrics* 59.1 (1984), pp. 69–116. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00150198408240738>.
- [17] H. Takezoe and F. Araoka. “Polar columnar liquid crystals”. In: *Liquid Crystals* 41.3 (2014), pp. 393–401. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2013.834079>.
- [18] O. D. Lavrentovich. “Ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal, a century in waiting”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117.26 (2020), pp. 14629–14631. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2008947117>.
- [19] H. Nishikawa, K. Shiroshita, H. Higuchi, Y. Okumura, Y. Haseba, S. Yamamoto, K. Sago, and H. Kikuchi. “A Fluid Liquid-Crystal Material with Highly Polar Order”. In: *Advanced Materials* 29.43 (2017), p. 1702354. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201702354>.
- [20] R. J. Mandle, S. J. Cowling, and J. W. Goodby. “A nematic to nematic transformation exhibited by a rod-like liquid crystal”. In: *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 19 (2017), pp. 11429–11435. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP00456G>.

- [21] A. Mertelj, L. Cmok, N. Sebastián, R. J. Mandle, R. R. Parker, A. C. Whitwood, J. W. Goodby, and M. Čopič. “Splay Nematic Phase”. In: *Physical Review X* 8 (2018), p. 041025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevX.8.041025>.
- [22] N. Sebastián, L. Cmok, R. J. Mandle, M. R. de la Fuente, I. D. Olenik, M. Čopič, and A. Mertelj. “Ferroelectric-Ferroelastic Phase Transition in a Nematic Liquid Crystal”. In: *Physical Review Letter* 124 (2020), p. 037801. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.124.037801>.
- [23] X. Chen, E. Korblova, D. Dong, X. Wei, R. Shao, L. Radzihovsky, M. A. Glaser, J. E. Maclellan, D. Bedrov, D. M Walba, and N. A. Clark. “First-principles experimental demonstration of ferroelectricity in a thermotropic nematic liquid crystal: Polar domains and striking electro-optics”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 117.25 (2020), pp. 14021–14031. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002290117>.
- [24] M. Praveen Kumar, Jakub Karcz, Przemyslaw Kula, Smarajit Karmakar, and Surajit Dhara. “Giant Electroviscous Effects in a Ferroelectric Nematic Liquid Crystal”. In: *Physical Review Applied* 19 (2023), p. 044082. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.19.044082>.
- [25] R. J. Mandle, N. Sebastián, J. Martinez-Perdiguero, and A. Mertelj. “On the molecular origins of the ferroelectric splay nematic phase”. In: *Nature Communications* 12.1 (2021), p. 4962. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25231-0>.
- [26] R. J. Mandle. “A new order of liquids: polar order in nematic liquid crystals”. In: *Soft Matter* 18 (2022), pp. 5014–5020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SM00543C>.
- [27] R. J. Mandle. “In Silico Interactome of a Room-Temperature Ferroelectric Nematic Material”. In: *Crystals* 13.6 (2023). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst13060857>.
- [28] M. Bremer A. Manabe and M. Kraska. “Ferroelectric nematic phase at and below room temperature”. In: *Liquid Crystals* 48.8 (2021), pp. 1079–1086. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2021.1921867>.

- [29] X. Chen, V. Martinez, E. Korblova, G. Freychet, M. Zhernenkov, M. A. Glaser, C. Wang, C. Zhu, L. Radzihovsky, J. E. MacLennan, D. M. Walba, and N. A. Clark. “The smectic ZA phase: Antiferroelectric smectic order as a prelude to the ferroelectric nematic”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120.8 (2023), e2217150120. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2217150120>.
- [30] F. Caimi, G. Nava, R. Barboza, N. A. Clark, E. Korblova, D. M. Walba, T. Bellini, and L. Lucchetti. “Surface alignment of ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals”. In: *Soft Matter* 17 (2021), pp. 8130–8139. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1SM00734C>.
- [31] J. Li, H. Nishikawa, J. Kougo, J. Zhou, S. Dai, W. Tang, X. Zhao, Y. Hisai, M. Huang, and S. Aya. “Development of ferroelectric nematic fluids with giant-eps dielectricity and nonlinear optical properties”. In: *Science Advances* 7.17 (2021), eabf5047. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abf5047>.
- [32] S. Brown, E. Cruickshank, J. M. D. Storey, C. T. Imrie, D. Pocięcha, M. Majewska, A. Makal, and E. Gorecka. “Multiple Polar and Non-polar Nematic Phases”. In: *ChemPhysChem* 22.24 (2021), pp. 2506–2510. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.202100644>.
- [33] A. Erkoreka, J. Martinez-Perdiguero, R. J. Mandle, A. Mertelj, and N. Sebastián. “Dielectric spectroscopy of a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal and the effect of the sample thickness”. In: *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 387 (2023), p. 122566. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2023.122566>.
- [34] A. Erkoreka, A. Mertelj, M. Huang, S. Aya, N. Sebastián, and J. Martinez-Perdiguero. “Collective and non-collective molecular dynamics in a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal studied by broadband dielectric spectroscopy”. In: *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 159 (2023), p. 184502. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0173813>.
- [35] N. A. Clark, X. Chen, J. E. MacLennan, and M. A. Glaser. “Dielectric spectroscopy of ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals: Measuring the capacitance of insulating interfacial layers”. In: *arXiv* (2023). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.09784>.

- [36] F. Caimi, G. Nava, S. Fuschetto, L. Lucchetti, P. Paié, R. Osellame, X. Chen, N. A. Clark, M. A. Glaser, and T. Bellini. “Fluid superscreening and polarization following in confined ferroelectric nematics”. In: *Nature Physics* 19.11 (2023), pp. 1658–1666. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-023-02150-z>.
- [37] N. Sebastián, M. Čopič, and A. Mertelj. “Ferroelectric nematic liquid-crystalline phases”. In: *Physical Review E* 106 (2022), p. 021001. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.106.021001>.
- [38] A. K. Tagantsev. “Piezoelectricity and flexoelectricity in crystalline dielectrics”. In: *Physical Review B* 34 (1986), pp. 5883–5889. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.34.5883>.
- [39] S. Vafaei and M.Z. Podowski. “Theoretical analysis on the effect of liquid droplet geometry on contact angle”. In: *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 235.10 (2005), pp. 1293–1301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2005.02.026>.
- [40] W. A. Arthur and P. G. Alice. *Physical Chemistry of Surfaces*. Interscience publishers, New York, 1997. ISBN: 978-0-471-14873-9.
- [41] E. Fuchs, A. D. Wexler, A. H. Paulitsch-Fuchs, L. L.F. Agostinho, D. Yntema, and J. Woisetschläger. “The Armstrong experiment revisited”. In: *The European Physical Journal Special Topics* 223 (2014), 959–977. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjst/e2013-01924-x>.
- [42] Elmar Fuchs, J. Woisetschläger, K. Gatterer, E. Maier, R. Pecnik, G. Holler, and H. Eisenkölbl. “The floating water bridge”. In: *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* 40 (2007), p. 6112. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/40/19/052>.
- [43] Á. G. Marín and D. Lohse. “Building water bridges in air: Electrohydrodynamics of the floating water bridge”. In: *Physics of Fluids* 22.12 (2010), p. 122104. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3518463>.
- [44] K. Morawetz. “Theory of water and charged liquid bridges”. In: *Physical Review E* 86 (2012), p. 026302. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.86.026302>.

- [45] R. Namin, S. Lindi, A. Amjadi, N. Jafari, and P. Irajizad. “Experimental investigation of the stability of the floating water bridge”. In: *Physical Review E* 88 (2013), p. 033019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.88.033019>.
- [46] A. A. Aerov. “Why the water bridge does not collapse”. In: *Physical Review E* 84 (2011), p. 036314. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.84.036314>.
- [47] A. Widom, J. Swain, J. Silverberg, S. Sivasubramanian, and Y. N. Srivastava. “Theory of the Maxwell pressure tensor and the tension in a water bridge”. In: *Physical Review E* 80 (2009), p. 016301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.80.016301>.
- [48] C. Q. Sun. “Water electrification: Principles and applications”. In: *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* 282 (2020), p. 102188. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2020.102188>.
- [49] X. Pan, M. Hu, B. Xu, F. Wang, P. Huo, F. Chen, Z. Gu, and D. Deng. “Armstrong liquid bridge: Formation, evolution and breakup”. In: *Physical Review Fluids* 6 (2021), p. 093901. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.093901>.
- [50] R. Ma, Y. Zhou, and J. Liu. “Floating and flying ferrofluid bridges induced by external magnetic fields”. In: *Modern Physics Letters B* 29.09 (2015), p. 1550029. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217984915500293>.
- [51] R. Canu and M. Renault. “Linear stability analysis of a Newtonian ferrofluid cylinder under a magnetic field”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 915 (2020), A137. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2021.171>.
- [52] Y. Li, J. Zhu, H. Cheng, G. Li, H. Cho, M. Jiang, Q. Gao, and X. Zhang. “Developments of Advanced Electrospinning Techniques: A Critical Review”. In: *Advanced Materials Technologies* 6.11 (2021), p. 2100410. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202100410>.
- [53] A. L. Yarin, W. Kataphinan, and D. H. Reneker. “Branching in electrospinning of nanofibers”. In: *Journal of Applied Physics* 98.6 (2005), p. 064501. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2060928>.

- [54] A. Tokarev, O. Trotsenko, I. M. Griffiths, H. A. Stone, and S. Minko. “Magnetospinning of Nano- and Microfibers”. In: *Advanced Materials* 27.23 (2015), pp. 3560–3565. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201500374>.
- [55] *Wikipedia*. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ferrofluid>.
- [56] M. Zahn. “Magnetic Fluid and Nanoparticle Applications to Nanotechnology”. In: *Journal of Nanoparticle Research* 3 (2001), pp. 73–78. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1011497813424>.
- [57] R. E. Rosensweig, M. Zahn, and R. Shumovich. “Labyrinthine instability in magnetic and dielectric fluids”. In: *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 39.1 (1983), pp. 127–132. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-8853\(83\)90416-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-8853(83)90416-X).
- [58] M. Zahn and R. Shumovich. “Labyrinthine Instability in Dielectric Fluids”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications* IA-21 (1985), pp. 53 –61. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.1985.349643>.
- [59] D. Damjanovic, P. Muralt, and N. Setter. “Ferroelectric Sensors”. In: *Sensors Journal* 1 (2001), pp. 191 –206. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2001.954832>.
- [60] P. Oswald, A. Dequidt, and G. Poy. “Lehmann effect in Nematic and Cholesteric liquid crystals: a review”. In: *Liquid Crystals Reviews* 7 (2019), pp. 1–34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21680396.2019.1671244>.
- [61] J. L. Ericksen. “Anisotropic fluids”. In: *Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis* 4.1 (1959), 231 – 237. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00281389>.
- [62] J. L. Ericksen. “Conservation Laws for Liquid Crystals”. In: *Journal of Rheology* 5.1 (1961), 23 – 34. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1122/1.548883>.
- [63] F. M. Leslie. “Some constitutive equations for anisotropic fluids”. In: *The Quarterly Journal of Mechanics and Applied Mathematics* 19.3 (1966), pp. 357–370. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmam/19.3.357>.
- [64] P. Pieranski and M. H. Godinho. *Liquid crystals: New perspectives*. John Wiley & Sons, 2021.

- [65] B. Abou, J. Wesfreid, and S. Roux. “The normal field instability in ferrofluids: hexagon–square transition mechanism and wavenumber selection”. In: *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* 416 (2000), 217–237. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002211200000882X>.
- [66] C. Chen and Z.Y. Cheng. “An experimental study on Rosensweig instability of a ferrofluid droplet”. In: *Physics of Fluids* 20 (2008), p. 054105. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2929372>.
- [67] D. P. Jackson and B. Gantner. “Energetics of interacting magnetized domains”. In: *Physical Review E* 64 (2001), p. 056230. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.64.056230>.
- [68] D. P. Jackson and J. A. Miranda. “Controlling fingering instabilities in rotating ferrofluids”. In: *Physical Review E* 67 (2003), p. 017301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.67.017301>.
- [69] D. P. Jackson. “Orientational preference and predictability in a symmetric arrangement of magnetic drops”. In: *Physical Review E* 68 (2003), p. 035301. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.68.035301>.
- [70] J. A. Miranda, R. M. Oliveira, and D. P. Jackson. “Adhesion phenomena in ferrofluids”. In: *Physical Review E* 70 (2004), p. 036311. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.70.036311>.
- [71] D. P. Jackson. “Theory, experiment, and simulations of a symmetric arrangement of quasi-two-dimensional magnetic fluid drops”. In: *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* 289 (2005), pp. 188–191. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2004.11.055>.
- [72] N. J. Hillier and D. P. Jackson. “Width of a ferrofluid finger: Hysteresis and a double energy minimum”. In: *Physical Review E* 75 (2007), p. 036314. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.75.036314>.
- [73] D. P. Jackson and J. A. Miranda. “Confined ferrofluid droplet in crossed magnetic fields”. In: *The European Physical Journal E* 23 (2007), 389–396. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1140/epje/i2007-10199-x>.
- [74] D. P. Jackson. “Hysteresis and multiple stable configurations in a magnetic fluid system”. In: *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* 20.20 (2008), p. 204140. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/20/20/204140>.

- [75] B.E. Sørensen. “A revised Michel-Lévy interference colour chart based on first-principles calculations”. In: *European Journal of Mineralogy* 25 (2013), pp. 5–10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1127/0935-1221/2013/0025-2252>.
- [76] M. Shribak and R. Oldenbourg. “Techniques for Fast and Sensitive Measurements of Two-Dimensional Birefringence Distributions”. In: *Applied optics* 42 (2003), pp. 3009–3017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.42.003009>.
- [77] H. R. Brand, H. Pleiner, and F. Ziebert. “Macroscopic dynamics of polar nematic liquid crystals”. In: *Physical Review E* 74 (2006), p. 021713. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.74.021713>.
- [78] K. Perera, R. Saha, P. Nepal, R. Dharmarathna, M. S. H. Himel, M. Mostafa, A. Alex, R. Waroquet, R. Twieg, and A. Jákli. “Ferroelectric Nematic Droplets in their Isotropic Melt”. In: *Soft Matter* 19 (2023), pp. 347–354. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SM01395A>.
- [79] J. Yang, Y. Zou, W. Tang, J. Li, M. Huang, and S. Aya. “Spontaneous electric-polarization topology in confined ferroelectric nematics”. In: *Nature Communications* 13 (2022), p. 7806. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-35443-7>.
- [80] P. Kumari, B. Basnet, H. Wang, and O. Lavrentovich. “Ferroelectric nematic liquids with conics”. In: *Nature Communications* 14 (2023), p. 748. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36326-1>.
- [81] G. Bradski. *The OpenCV Library*. Vol. 25. Dr. Dobb’s J. Software Tools, 2000.
- [82] Y. Liu and S. T. Neely. “Suppression tuning of distortion-product otoacoustic emissions: Results from cochlear mechanics simulation”. In: *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 133.2 (2013), pp. 951–961. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4774279>.
- [83] J. Szydłowska, P. Majewski, M. Čepič, N. Vaupotic, P. Rybak, C. Imrie, R. Walker, E. Cruickshank, J. Storey, D. Pocięcha, and E. Gorecka. “Ferroelectric Nematic-Isotropic Liquid Critical End Point”. In: *Physical Review Letters* 130 (2023), p. 216802. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.130.216802>.

- [84] A. L. Barabási and H. E. Stanley. *Fractal Concepts in Surface Growth*. Cambridge University Press, 1995.
- [85] J. T. Gostick, Z. A. Khan, T. G. Tranter, M. D. R. Kok, M. Agnaou, M. Sadeghi, and R. Jervis. “PoreSpy: A Python Toolkit for Quantitative Analysis of Porous Media Images”. In: *Journal of Open Source Software* 4.37 (2019), p. 1296. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01296>.
- [86] R. Barboza, S. Marni, F. Ciciulla, M. Ali, G. Nava, F. Caimi, A. Zaltron, N. A. Clark, T. Bellini, and L. Lucchetti. “Explosive electrostatic instability of ferroelectric liquid droplets on ferroelectric solid surfaces”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 119 (2022). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2207858119>.
- [87] C. Bechinger, R. Leonardo, H. Löwen, C. Reichhardt, G. Volpe, and G. Volpe. “Active Particles in Complex and Crowded Environments”. In: *Review of Modern Physics* 88 (2016). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.88.045006>.
- [88] G. Volpe, S. Gigan, and G. Volpe. “Simulation of the active Brownian motion of a microswimmer”. In: *American Journal of Physics* 82 (2014), p. 659. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4870398>.
- [89] J. R. Taylor. *Classical mechanics*. Vol. 1. Springer, 2005. ISBN: 1-891389-22-X.
- [90] S. Rupitsch. “Simulation of Piezoelectric Sensor and Actuator Devices”. In: *Piezoelectric Sensors and Actuators* (2019), pp. 83–126. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-57534-5_4.
- [91] URL: <https://www.pi-usa.us/en/products/piezo-motors-stages-actuatorsce-gallery-71779>.
- [92] L. Cmok, V. Coda, N. Sebastian, A. Mertelj, M. Zgonik, S. Aya, M. Huang, G. Montemezzani, and I. Drevensek-Olenik. “Running streams of a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal on a lithium niobate surface”. In: *Liquid Crystals* 50.7-10 (2023), pp. 1478–1485. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2022.2161018>.

- [93] R. Barboza, S. Bahwi, S. Marni, and L. Lucchetti. “On the Behavior of Ferroelectric Liquid Droplets in the Vicinity of a Ferroelectric Solid”. In: *Crystals* 13 (2023), p. 750. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst13050750>.
- [94] A. Sterle, L. Cmok, N. Sebastián, A. Mertelj, Y. Kong, X. Zhang, and I. Drevenšek-Olenik. “Light-induced dynamics of liquid-crystalline droplets on the surface of iron-doped lithium niobate crystals”. In: *Optical Materials Express* 13.1 (2023), pp. 282–294. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1364/OME.477717>.
- [95] D. Tanaka, T. Tsukada, M. Furukawa, S. Wada, and Y. Kuroiwa. “Thermal Reliability of Alkaline Niobate-Based Lead-Free Piezoelectric Ceramics”. In: *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics* 48 (2009). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1143/JJAP.48.09KD08>.
- [96] C. Parton-Barr, H. F. Gleeson, and R. J. Mandle. “Room-temperature ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal showing a large and diverging density”. In: *Soft Matter* 20.3 (2024), pp. 672–680. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SM01282D>.
- [97] R. Stannarius, . Nemeş, and A. Eremin. “Plucking a liquid chord: Mechanical response of a liquid crystal filament”. In: *Physical Review E* 72 (2005), p. 020702. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.72.020702>.
- [98] A. Eremin, A. Jarosik, H. Nádas, M. Schwidder, A. Manabe, M. Bremer, and M. Klasen-Memmer. “Fluid fibres in true 3D ferroelectric liquids”. In: *arXiv* (2023). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.12412>.
- [99] C. Zhang, M. Gao, R. Ribeiro de Almeida, W. Weissflog, O. Lavrentovich, and A. Jákli. “Polarization-Modulated Bent-Core Liquid Crystal Thin Films without Layer Undulation”. In: *Physical Review Letters* 122 (2019). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.122.137801>.
- [100] R. Saha, P. Nepal, C. Feng, M. S. Hossain, M. Fukuto, R. Li, J.T. Gleeson, S. Sprunt, R. J. Twieg, and A. Jákli. “Multiple ferroelectric nematic phases of a highly polar liquid crystal compound”. In: *Liquid Crystals* 49.13 (2022), pp. 1784–1796. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2022.2069297>.
- [101] F.A. Morrison. *Understanding Rheology*. Oxford University Press, 2001. ISBN: 0-19-514166-0.

- [102] J. Chen, C. Wang, N. Wei, R. Wan, and Y. Gao. “3D flexible water channel: stretchability of nanoscale water bridge”. In: *Nanoscale* 8 (2016), pp. 5676–5681. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5NR08072J>.

List of publications

- [P1] M. T. Máthé, Á. Buka, A. Jákli, and P. Salamon. "Ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal thermomotor". In: *Physical Review E* 105 (2022), pp. L052701. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.105.L052701>
- [P2] M. T. Máthé, B. Farkas, L. Péter, Á. Buka, A. Jákli, and P. Salamon, "Electric field-induced interfacial instability in a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal". In: *Scientific Reports* 13 (2023), pp. 6981. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-34067-1>
- [P3] M. T. Máthé, M. S. H. Himel, A. Adaka, J. T. Gleeson, S. Sprunt, P. Salamon, and A. Jákli, "Liquid Piezoelectric Materials: Linear Electromechanical Effect in Fluid Ferroelectric Nematic Liquid Crystals", In: *Advanced Functional Materials* (2024), pp. 2314158. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202314158>
- [P4] M. T. Máthé, K. Perera, Á. Buka, P. Salamon, and A. Jákli, "Fluid Ferroelectric Filaments". In: *Advanced Science* (2023), pp. 2305950. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202305950>
- [P5] M. T. Máthé, H. Nishikawa, F. Araoka, A. Jákli and P. Salamon. "Ramification and labyrinthine instabilities in a ferroelectric nematic fluid exposed to electric fields". (in preparation)
- [P6] M. T. Máthé, H. Nishikawa, F. Araoka, A. Jákli and P. Salamon, "Electrically Activated Ferroelectric Nematic Microrobots". (in preparation)

The publications below are not related to the subject of this Dissertation:

- [P7] M. T. Máthé, Á. Buka, and P. Salamon, "Defects induced by anchoring transitions of nematic fluids at solid and gas interfaces". In: *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 336 (2021), pp. 116074. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2021.116074>.
- [P8] Z. Karaszi, M. T. Máthé, P. Salamon, Á. Buka, and A. Jákli, "Electric field induced buckling of inversion walls in lens-shape liquid crystal droplets. In: *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 365 (2022), pp. 120177. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.120177>

- [P9]** Z. Karaszi, M. T. Máthé, P. Salamon, Á. Buka, and A. Jákli, "Lens-shaped nematic liquid crystal droplets with negative dielectric anisotropy in electric and magnetic fields. In: *Liquid Crystals* 50 (2023), pp. 393-402, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2022.2134594>
- [P10]** Á. Buka, P. Salamon, M. T. Máthé, Z. Karaszi, and A. Jákli, "Nematic liquid crystals in lens shape geometry", In: *Liquid Crystals* 50 (2023), pp. 1582-1598. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678292.2023.2168307>
- [P11]** P. Salamon, M. T. Máthé, Á. Buka, and A. Jákli, "Hangolható hibahelyek nematikus folyadékkristály-cseppekben". In: *Fizikai Szemle* 73 (2023), pp. 120-124

Theses

1. I showed by optical measurements that, when using a homeotropic alignment layer, an anchoring transition occurs during the nematic - ferroelectric nematic phase transition in liquid crystal droplets. I showed that the director and the spontaneous polarisation have tangential structure in the ferroelectric nematic phase, which was explained by electrostatic reasons. [P1]
2. I discovered a new thermohydrodynamic effect, which is observable only in the ferroelectric nematic phase. The phenomenon involves the induction of flow in sessile droplets by a temperature gradient. I determined the properties of the phenomenon in different temperature gradients and in the presence of electric field. I determined the temperature dependence of the flow rate. I interpreted the phenomenon as a cross effect due to the lack of mirror symmetry of the ferroelectric nematic phase.[P1]
3. I demonstrated experimentally that in free-surface ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals, the alternating electric field induces a new type of surface instability, which we have termed ramification. I have investigated the instability in various geometries and determined the dependence of the threshold voltage on frequency and temperature. The Hausdorff dimension of the fractal structure resulting from the instability was derived. By experiments and simulations, I revealed that the insulating layer on the surface of the electrodes plays a key role in the development of the instability. Furthermore, I demonstrated by optical measurements that the polarisation in the branches formed during the instability is parallel to the longitudinal axis of the branches, leading to the repulsion of nearby droplets.[P2],[P5]
4. I showed that the Rosensweig type labyrinthine instability can be observed in ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals in alternating electric fields and that its threshold voltage is orders of magnitude smaller than in the dielectrics studied so far. I determined the threshold voltage as a function of frequency and parameters of the sample geometry.[P5]
5. I determined the morphological phase diagram of ferroelectric nematic liquid bridges as a function of voltage and frequency. I showed that in a specific

regime, droplet fragmentation and active self-propulsive behaviour can be observed, thus revealing a new two-dimensional artificial active particle system. By tracking the particles and using statistical methods, I determined the characteristic properties of the motion. I confirmed that the average velocity of the particles is controllable by the applied voltage.[P6]

6. I demonstrated by both acoustic and direct experimental methods that a linear electromechanical effect can be observed in ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals. I measured the frequency and voltage dependence of the phenomenon and determined the converse piezoelectric coefficient of a ferroelectric nematic liquid crystal.[P3],[P6]
7. I showed that stable fibres with aspect ratios orders of magnitude larger than the Rayleigh limit can be drawn from ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals. I demonstrated experimentally that the fibres can be further stabilised by an external static electric field and can be vibrated by an alternating field. I also presented novel measurement methods to determine the spontaneous polarisation and viscosity of the material.[P4]

Tézisek

1. Optikai mérésekkel megmutattam, hogy homeotrop felületi orientáló réteg használata esetén a nematikus – ferroelektromos nematikus fázisátmenet során felületi orientációs fázisátalakulás történik folyadékkristály cseppekben. A ferroelektromos nematikus fázisban tangenciális direktor és polarizáció struktúrárt találtam, melyet elektrosztatikai okokkal magyaráztam.[P1]
2. Felfedeztem egy új termohidrodinamikai effektust, ami kizárólag a ferroelektromos nematikus fázisban figyelhető meg. A jelenség során csepp geometriában áramlás indukálható hőmérséklet gradiens létrehozásával. Megállapítottam a jelenség tulajdonságait különféle hőmérséklet gradiensekben és elektromos tér jelenlétében. Meghatároztam az áramlási sebesség hőmérséklet függését. A jelenséget egy keresztteffektusként értelmeztem, mely a ferroelektromos nematikus fázis nem szokványos szimmetriájának a következménye.[P1]
3. Kísérletileg igazoltam, hogy szabad felületű ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristályokban a mintára kapcsolt váltakozó elektromos tér egy újfajta felületi instabilitás kialakulásához vezet, melyet ágasodásnak nevezünk. Az instabilitást többféle geometriában vizsgáltam és meghatároztam a küszöb feszültség frekvencia és hőmérséklet függését. Megállapítottam az instabilitás következtében kialakuló fraktál struktúra Hausdorff dimenzióját. Kísérletekkel és szimulációkkal beláttam, hogy az instabilitás kialakulásában kulcsszerepe van az elektródák felületét bevonó szigetelő rétegnek. Továbbá optikai mérésekkel bizonyítottam, hogy az instabilitás során kialakuló ágakban a polarizáció az ágak hossz tengelyével párhuzamos, ami a közeli cseppek egymás közti taszításához vezet. [P2],[P5]
4. Megmutattam, hogy a Rosensweig féle labirintus instabilitás ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristályokban is megfigyelhető váltakozó elektromos térben és a küszöb feszültsége nagyságrendekkel kisebb, mint az eddig vizsgált dielektrikumokban. Meghatároztam a küszöb feszültséget a frekvencia és a minta geometriai paramétereinek függvényében.[P5]
5. Meghatároztam a ferroelektromos nematikus folyadék hidak morfológiai fázisdiagramját a mintára kapcsolt feszültség és frekvencia függvényében.

Megmutattam, hogy egy adott régióban a cseppek felaprózódása és aktív önhajtó viselkedése figyelhető meg, ezzel felfedezve egy újfajta kétdimenziós mesterséges aktív részecskerendszert. A részecskék követésével és statisztikai módszerekkel meghatároztam a mozgás jellemzőit. Igazoltam, hogy a részecskék átlagsebessége a feszültséggel hangolható.[P6]

6. Akusztikai és közvetlen kísérleti módszerrel is igazoltam, hogy lineáris elektromechanikai effektus figyelhető meg ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristályokban. Meghatároztam a jelenség frekvencia illetve feszültségfüggését és egy vizsgált ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristály inverz piezoelektromos együtthatóját. [P3],[P6]
7. Megmutattam, hogy ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristályokból a Rayleigh-limitnél nagyságrendekkel nagyobb oldalarányú stabil szálak húzhatók. Kísérletileg bizonyítottam, hogy a szálak külső állandó elektromos térrel tovább stabilizálhatók és váltakozó térrel rezgésbe hozhatók. Bemutattam továbbá újfajta mérési módszereket melyekkel meghatároztam az anyag spontán polarizációját és viszkozitását.[P4]

Summary

The creation of the first three-dimensional liquid with ferroelectric properties was achieved a few years ago. The ferroelectric nematic liquid crystals exhibit huge spontaneous electric polarisation while keeping fluidity. The topic of the presented PhD work covers the thermo- and electromechanical cross effects and electric field induced instabilities in ferroelectric nematics.

The unusual symmetry of the phase allowed the discovery of new cross effects in ferroelectric nematic liquids. We presented an extraordinary thermohydrodynamical effect in sessile droplets, where a temperature gradient can induce stable flow of the material. Furthermore, we showed the presence of inverse piezoelectricity, as alternating electric field induced mechanical vibration in ferroelectric nematic films.

Interfacial instabilities in liquid bridges and in sessile droplets were also investigated in presence of external electric fields. The primary instability called ramification induces the growth of stable branches from the liquid leading to the formation of fractal-like structures. A secondary instability resembles to the Rosensweig type labyrinthine instability observed in ferrofluids and in dielectrics, nonetheless in our case the required threshold field was orders of magnitude smaller. To understand these instabilities, various experiments and simulations were conducted.

We also presented an extraordinary state of liquid bridges behaving as artificial active particles called "febots", induced by the interfacial instabilities in a specific voltage and frequency range. The characteristic properties and statistical behavior of the febot motion were studied. The average velocity of the active particles shows unique controllability via the applied voltage.

Finally, the nature of filament forming ability of ferroelectric nematics is revealed. We presented how ferroelectric fluid fibres are stabilised without and with the presence of an external electric field. Additionally, we determined physical parameters of ferroelectric nematics, such as spontaneous electric polarisation and viscosity by new measurement techniques.

Összefoglaló

Néhány évvel ezelőtt sikerült előállítani az első ferroelektromos tulajdonságokkal rendelkező folyadékokat. A ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékkristályok óriási spontán elektromos polarizációval rendelkeznek, miközben megőrzik folyékonyságukat. A bemutatott doktori munka témája a termo- és elektromechanikai keresztteffektusok és az elektromos mező által kiváltott instabilitások ferroelektromos nematikusokban.

A fázis szokatlan szimmetriája tette lehetővé újfajta keresztteffektusok jelenlétének megfigyelését ferroelektromos nematikus folyadékokban. Bemutatunk egy különleges termohidrodinamikai jelenséget cseppekben, ahol a hőmérséklet gradiens stabil áramlást indukálhat az anyagban. Továbbá kimutattuk az inverz piezoelektromosság, mint váltakozó elektromos mező által kiváltott mechanikai rezgés jelenlétét ferroelektromos nematikus filmekben.

Folyadékhidak és cseppek felületi instabilitását is vizsgáltuk külső elektromos tér jelenlétében. Az ágasodásnak nevezett elsődleges instabilitás stabil folyadéknúlványok megjelenését idézi elő a kontaktvonal körül, ami fraktálszerű struktúrák kialakulásához vezet. A másodlagos instabilitás hasonlít a ferrofluidokban és dielektrikumokban megfigyelt Rosensweig-féle labirintus instabilitáshoz, esetünkben azonban a szükséges küszöbtér nagyságrendekkel kisebb. Az instabilitások mélyebb megértése érdekében különféle kísérleteket és szimulációkat végeztünk.

Bemutattuk a "febot"-nak nevezett mesterséges aktív részecskéként viselkedő folyadékhidak meghökkentő állapotát is, amelyet a határfelületi instabilitások idéznek elő egy adott feszültség- és frekvenciatartományban. A febotok mozgásának tulajdonságait kísérleti és statisztikai módszerekkel is vizsgáltuk és azt találtuk, hogy az aktív részecskék átlagos sebessége az alkalmazott feszültséggel jelentős mértékben szabályozható.

Végül feltártuk a ferroelektromos nematikusok szálképző képességének természetét. Bemutattuk, hogyan stabilizálódnak a ferroelektromos folyadékszálak külső elektromos tér nélkül és annak jelenlétében. Emellett új mérési technikákkal meghatároztuk a ferroelektromos nematikusok fizikai paramétereit, mint például a spontán elektromos polarizációt és a viszkozitást.